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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents results of work related to in situ measurements, sea ice remote sensing products and reanalysis products in the Fram Strait and in the Arctic Ocean north of Svalbard. The results also include examples of how various observational data and models can be combined and used to describe the ice-ocean environment in the region.

A number of **ocean and sea ice statistical products** based on long timeseries of repeated oceanographic ship-based surveys, year-round measurements on fixed moorings, and sea ice concentration products are presented. Analysed ocean physical variables include measured in situ subsurface ocean temperature and salinity, and their derived products such as water mass properties, layer thickness and relative ocean heat content. Mean spatial fields and properties averaged for specific water masses as well as mean annual cycle, long-term monthly means are calculated and presented as well as annual and monthly anomalies for selected parameters. A collection of ocean and sea ice products, with examples presented in the report, will be further exploited to provide integrated time series of ocean observations via a dedicated website. The products will be presented as plots and data files (NetCDF) that can be used for calibration and validation of numerical models and as a background for ocean climate and environmental assessments.

The climate induced environmental changes in the Arctic will change both the mechanisms and processes producing natural ocean sound, change the ocean stratification, and increased accessibility and traffic to the Arctic region will change the amount of sound from human activities. To assess the effect of the changes in the Arctic it is important to benchmark the current state of the Arctic acoustic observing capacity and to make recommendations for future sustained acoustic observations. A processing chain for passive acoustic products from distributed acoustic arrays into standard formats (NetCDF), including quality flags, has been established. Furthermore, reanalysis results produced for INTAROS using the GECCO model and 4 DVAR (Gukun et al 2020) has been used as input to the Bellhop (ray trace model) to better understand capabilities and limitations in acoustic tomography, geo-positioning and communication. Results from this work has been presented in our proceeding papers that have been produced and submitted to the Proceedings of Meetings on Acoustics (POMA).

Results from the remote sensing work are presented in other reports (D6.20, D6.22, D6.23 and D6.24).

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1 INTRODUCTION

This report describes several studies that have analyzed in situ data, remote sensing, and models aiming to describe the ice-ocean and acoustical environment in the Fram Strait and the area north of Svalbard. The studies provide important contributions to climate and environmental research, monitoring and assessment in the region.

The report is organized into two major topics:

- 1) Ocean and ice statistics derived from in situ observations and remote sensing. The statistics includes essential ocean variables such as subsurface ocean temperature, subsurface salinity, heat content, and sea ice concentration. The responsible partner is IOPAN.
- 2) The Fram Strait acoustic environment is described through observations, and modelling. The responsible partner is NERSC.

To provide input to the Synthesis report of WP6 the following key questions are addressed:

- 1) What were the main activities and results from the work?
- 2) What data and models were used?
- 3) Who are the stakeholders/users who will benefit from the results?
- 4) How should the results be further developed and exploited after the end of the project?

1.1 Ocean and ice statistics from in situ observations and remote sensing

1.1.1 What were the main activities and results from the work ?

The main activities were focused on obtaining ocean statistics from oceanographic in situ measurements in the Nordic Seas and Arctic Ocean, collected by IOPAN in the last two decades. Statistical analysis of oceanographic data collections from ship-borne measurements during annual summer field campaigns AREX and mooring observations north of Svalbard aimed to characterize long-term changes in ocean climate and variability of ocean key physical variables on different time scales. The results include spatial maps and time series of key ocean variables (temperature, salinity, ocean currents) and derived properties (e.g., Atlantic layer properties, ocean heat content) in selected locations. Background statistics of sea ice concentration in the mooring region were obtained based on satellite remote sensing. The ultimate goal is to aggregate in one place (website with open access) long-term series of in situ observations (including their statistics) and results of integrative analysis of measured ocean variables and derived quantities together with available sea ice and atmospheric information for further use by external users.

1.1.2 What data and models were used?

To obtain large-scale maps of ocean properties and their statistics and long-term time series of key ocean climate variables, in situ ship-borne measurements from the IOPAN AREX long-term monitoring program (2000-2020) were used. To obtain statistics of seasonal to interannual variability of ocean physical parameters, in situ observations collected at three INTAROS moorings north of Svalbard were employed in combination with mooring data from earlier deployments in this region. Sea ice statistics for the mooring region north of Svalbard were obtained from available remote sensing product. Data from in situ measurements of sea ice at moorings are under processing and their statistics will be added at the later stage when the final data product is ready.

1.1.3 Who are the stakeholders/users who will benefit from the results?

Data will be used in further research activities focused on the ocean physical state and dynamics in the region of the Atlantic water inflow towards and into the Arctic Ocean. Time series of variables measured by moored instruments can be also used to provide derived products for other research activities, e.g. environmental background for biological or carbon system studies in the central Arctic. Potential users include scientists across a wide range of different disciplines, including modelers working with ocean and climate forecast and prediction or groups working on assessments of Arctic ecosystems and natural resources. Interactions between

ocean and sea ice and ocean-ice statistics in poorly observed parts of the Arctic Ocean can be of a special interest for planning and operating future shipping routes in the opening for navigation Arctic areas.

1.1.4 How should the results be further developed and exploited after the end of the project?

The derived data products, including spatial maps, time series and basic statistics of measured ocean physical variables from ship-borne and mooring measurements will be available as visual information (graphic files) and data products in netCDF format from the dedicated IOPAN website and/or data base. The long-term time series will contribute to different reports on the ocean and climate states, e.g. to the ICES Report on Ocean Climate (IROC), published annually. Derived data products will be available for providing the physical background for the biogeochemical and biological studies and ecosystem assessments. They will be also available for validation of and assimilation into numerical models and for the purpose of optimizing components of a future Arctic observing system. Presented results will be also used in the PhD work of the IOPAN PhD student (Agata Grynczel), working in INTAROS. The results are also used as input to the work on the Fram Strait acoustic environment.

1.2 The Fram Strait Acoustic environment from observations and modelling

1.2.1 What were the main activities and results from the work?

The results from our studies were compiled and presented in four proceeding papers that have been submitted to the Proceedings of Meetings on Acoustics (POMA) with editorial review.

The papers are as follows:

Title: Analysis of passive acoustic in situ observing systems in the Arctic Ocean using ARCMAP. Information about 11 Arctic observing systems that includes ocean sound are extracted from the ARCMAP system, which provides maps, statistics and other information about the observing systems in the Arctic (<https://arcmap.nersc.no>). The information includes location, operational period, data storage, data access, and funding situation. In our analysis we find that the typical system providing ocean sound is focused, project based, funded at the national level and has not advanced routines for data storage and management. (Accepted)

Title: A dataset of underwater passive acoustic recordings from a 2-year mooring deployment in Fram Strait (UNDER-ICE). The data set contains aggregated and quality controlled acoustic recordings from the UNDER-ICE acoustic thermometry experiment, which deployed 5 moorings in Fram Strait from 2014-2016. Acoustic recordings from these long deep-water moorings differ from bottom-mounted hydrophones as they can be influenced by noise from the mooring itself due to cable strumming in strong currents. From this work we recommend that moorings for passive acoustic recordings should be preferably placed at sites with weak ocean currents. Acoustic data are prepared for publication in Norwegian Marine Data Center. (Accepted)

Title: Analysis of signal propagation in the UNDER-ICE experiment During the UNDER-ICE experiment transmissions from two sweeper sources were made every third hour along 7 different transects. Analysis of the acoustic receptions from the northernmost transect, a 180 km long transect from East to West at 80 N across the strait, showed that the 90 s long signal vanished during some time periods. However, no specific cause has yet been identified. In future we recommend to obtain recordings of the source signals on the mooring that is transmitting to check if the source was transmitting. This feature comes at a cost such as increased battery consumption and data storage requirement. In the last paper we demonstrate how use of ice-ocean models, combined with acoustic modelling, can be a powerful and useful combination, both in terms of planning and analysis of results from experiments. (accepted)

Title: Using ice-ocean environment from reanalysis into Bellhop to better understand sound propagation in the Fram Strait In this paper we use acoustic modelling to study how acoustic signals propagates between two moorings separated by 200 km in the Fram Strait. The numerical simulations confirm that the oceanographic conditions can make it hard to transmit signal from a source outside the ice edge to a receiver array inside the ice edge. Changing the configuration of source and receiver array can improve the receptions. (resubmitted)

1.2.2 What data and models were used?

1. The ARCMAP database https://arcmapping.nersc.no/#ac_3575/2/90.0/0.0
2. The reanalysis produced for Task 6.3 available at <http://thredds.nersc.no/thredds/gecco/catalog.html>
3. The acoustic propagation model Bellhop. More information are found at <https://oalib-acoustics.org/AcousticsToolbox/Bellhop-2010-1.pdf>
4. Acoustic data from UNDER-ICE moorings. Submitted as data publication. XBT sections between moorings has been submitted to NMDC. <https://doi.org/doi:10.21335/NMDC-NERSC-1232980327>

1.2.3 Who are the stakeholders/users who will benefit from the results?

Climate and Environmental monitoring. ‘Ocean Sound’, like ocean temperature, is an important physical parameter that directly influence the well-being of marine life. Therefore, managers, researchers, and operators in the Arctic should use ocean sound data and results as part of their environmental and climate assessments. There are large gaps in monitoring of ocean sound, and one of the important gaps is that there is no complete inventory of where acoustic observations are made. ARCMAP can be used as a quantitative basis for, e.g., gap analyses or planning processes about deployments of new acoustic equipment in the Arctic, negotiations versus funding agencies or other stakeholders, development of European or international research projects or programs, etc. The filtered information is differentiated on various aspects of sustainability status, such as financial support, maintenance support, placement inside international organizations, data management and accessibility.

Research, Innovation, and Technology development. Ambient noise characteristics, stemming either from natural sources or human activities, and acoustic propagation conditions influences capabilities in underwater acoustic communication, navigations, and observation technology. Knowledge about the acoustic environment is useful for technology developers to tailor and improve acoustic technologies for the Arctic. Furthermore, long term implementation of future multipurpose acoustic network can support innovation activities within underwater observing technology (e.g. improved geo-positioning of gliders and subsurface floats operating under ice) and technology for search and rescue operations (e.g. localization of transmitting objects).

1.2.4 How should the results be further developed and exploited after the end of the project?

Ocean sound is an important parameter describing the living conditions for life in the ocean, and is listed under indicator 11 in the Marine Strategy Framework Directive https://ec.europa.eu/environment/marine/good-environmental-status/descriptor-11/index_en.htm. The importance of monitoring underwater acoustic environment has also been recognized as an Essential Ocean Variable (EOV) under GOOS (https://www.goosocean.org/index.php?option=com_oe&task=viewDocumentRecord&docID=22567). The International Quiet Ocean Experiment (IQOE) (<https://www.iqoe.org>) have worked hard to guide the formulation and implementation of the ‘ocean sound’ as a EOV. IQOE contributes to operationalization of acoustic monitoring under GOOS including steps to make data intercomparable. An important part of this effort is to ensure that instruments are calibrated, communicate how acoustic instrumentation should be integrated into different platforms, how data are processed and formatted, and how products are presented for different users.

Acoustic recordings produce a lot of data which need to be processed and quality controlled. Although work have been done within INTAROS, the processing chain of passive acoustic observations from long arrays in moorings still need to be streamlined to become more operational. In this work we recommend considering using machine learning (ML) e.g. in recognizing poor data, and recognizing different known signals e.g. shipping, seismic and known mammal vocalization. ML is on everyone’s lips, but it is important to be critical and use of ML where it is beneficial. The most important is that the operationalization of the data delivery chain follows standards, quality control procedures, and produce useful and comparable products for the different users.

The Arctic Council Working group PAME delivered a status report in 2019 about ambient noise in the Arctic <https://www.pame.is/projects/arctic-marine-shipping/underwater-noise-in-the-arctic>. The report points out the importance of increasing the knowledge base through improved observing capacity and improved modelling. A particular scientific problem that needs to be addressed is to include the effect of ice on acoustic propagation. Another topic is to secure sustained funding for long term monitoring of ‘ocean sound’ in key regions.

Multi purpose acoustic networks such as those implemented in the Fram Strait (DAMOCLES, ACOBAR and UNDER-ICE) are used for thermometry, passive acoustic and underwater GPS for gliders and floats (Mikhalevsky et al 2015, and Worcester et al. 2020). Passive acoustic data from such multipurpose acoustic networks are an important source of year-round acoustic recordings. A total of 9 moorings has provided acoustic recordings. Passive acoustic data from most of these mooring have been processed and published in the Norwegian Marine Data Center. These data will be further analyzed and compared to other data in the region.

In acoustic network known acoustic signal (200-300 Hz) are sent out and received at fixed positions. This makes it possible to study acoustic propagation in a controlled experiment. Our analysis of acoustic data from ACOBAR and UNDER-ICE show that gliders and floats cannot expect to get signal everywhere in the water column. This indicate that the vehicles or floats need to be programmed to listen at optimal depths based on the sound speed profile. Furthermore, the arrival structure in the Fram Strait is so that it might be difficult to do through standard arrival time detection (eg. Sagen et al. 2017). This means that the detection of signals must be more adaptive to the arrival structure in different regions of the Arctic. In paper 3 and 4 we show how scientists can use reanalysis as input to acoustic propagation systems to design future acoustic systems for optimized for thermometry, geo-positioning, and acoustic communication. This process will be refined and streamlined in coming projects. Several students (bachelor, masters, and PhD) are working with data collected during ACOBAR, UNDER-ICE, INTAROS, and CAATEX.

Reference

Sagen, H., Peter F. Worcester; Matthew A. Dzieciuch; et al. (2017) Resolution, identification, and stability of broadband acoustic arrivals in Fram Strait. *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, 143.z

Mikhalevsky P., H Sagen et al.. *Multipurpose Acoustic Networks in the Integrated Arctic Ocean Observing System*. Arctic 2015; Volum 68.(5) s.1-17.

Worcester, P., M. A. Dzieciuch, H. Sagen, Ocean Acoustics in the Rapidly Changing Arctic. *Acoustics Today Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* 2020; Volum 16.(1).

2 OCEAN AND ICE STATISTICS FROM LONG-TERM IN SITU OBSERVATIONS IN THE ARCTIC

Long-term measurements collected in the fixed points or over the repeated grids of regular stations and sections offer a unique opportunity to estimate variability of key ocean variables over different temporal and spatial scales. Long observational time series allow to obtain basic statistics which characterize ocean climate in the selected regions (e.g. ocean basins) or key locations (e.g. ocean gateways), including mean fields of essential ocean variables (EOVs) and their anomalies from the long-term mean state.

In the deliverable D.6.13 we present exemplary statistics, calculated from two collections of observational data, covering the domain of the Atlantic water (AW) inflow towards the Arctic Ocean (the eastern Norwegian and Greenland seas, and the eastern Fram Strait) and the key location where the Atlantic inflow joins the Arctic Ocean Boundary Current north of Svalbard in the western Eurasian Basin). In situ observations of key ocean variables in the Atlantic domain were collected during the annual (summer) large-scale ship-borne surveys under the IOPAN long-term monitoring program AREX, started in 1996. North of Svalbard, quasi-continuous measurements of physical ocean variables, including subsurface temperature and salinity, and subsurface ocean currents have been collected at different oceanographic moorings since 2012 (since 2017 as a part of the INTAROS in situ observational activities). To provide the background information for analysis and interpretation of mooring measurements north of Svalbard and the impact of ocean heat content in the upstream inflow area (measured during AREX surveys, the basic statistics of sea ice concentration were obtained from available remote sensing products).

2.1 Ocean climate statistic from the IOPAN long-term monitoring program AREX in the Atlantic inflow domain of the Nordic Seas, Fram Strait and north of Svalbard

The main aim of the IOPAN long-term monitoring program AREX and annual summer surveys, carried by RV *Oceania* for the last 30 years in the Nordic Seas and Fram Strait, is to recognize and describe processes responsible for changing ocean climate and marine ecosystem in the sub-Arctic and Arctic region with a special focus on the European Arctic (Walczowski, 2017). A large-scale study area of the poleward flow of Atlantic water in the eastern Nordic Seas and Fram Strait has been covered with annually repeated ship-borne measurements on a regular station grid since 1996. Most of regularly repeated stations are distributed along several zonal sections (some of them covered since 1996 while a full set of standard sections was established in 2000), crossing the continental shelf break at the right angle and extending towards the deep basin. On the eastern side, the AREX oceanographic sections are limited by the Barents Sea shelf break and the shelf area west and north of Svalbard. To the west, the sections cross the Arctic Front, located above the system of underwater ridges (the Mohn and Knipovich ridges) and limiting the extent of Atlantic water in the Nordic Seas. The zonal sections following the Atlantic water inflow from the Norwegian Sea to the northern Fram Strait allow to assess transformation of water masses originating from the North Atlantic and advected northward. Two meridional sections, one from the northern Norway towards the Bear Island and one between the Bear Island and the southernmost tip of Svalbard (Sørkapp), cover the eastward flow of Atlantic water to the Barents Sea. The data collected under the observational program AREX every year, in the same way, during the same season (in June-July) provide time series of key ocean variables which allow monitoring changes of the Arctic oceanic climate and environment.

Physical ocean variables, including ocean temperature, salinity, pressure, dissolved oxygen and fluorescence were measured on each station occupied during the AREX surveys in the full water column from the surface down to the near-bottom depth. In the last two decades, additional measurements of ocean currents were collected during the AREX surveys on all occupied stations with the LADCP (full depth) and underway (including stations) with the VM-ADCP (in the upper 200-300m). Data processing chain for the AREX CTD measurements is described in the deliverable D.2.X.

Derived properties, obtained from *in situ* measured key physical variables, include mean properties of different water masses (mean temperature, salinity, density, layer thickness), in particular of the Atlantic water, defined

according to selected parametrizations. In the examples shown below, Atlantic water is defined after Walczowski (2016) with temperature $T > 0^{\circ}\text{C}$ and salinity $S > 34.92$ but other parametrizations, e.g. based on density rather than salinity (after Rudels et al., 1995), and distinguishing between warm ($T > 2^{\circ}\text{C}$) and cold ($0^{\circ}\text{C} > T > 2^{\circ}\text{C}$) Atlantic water (after Schlichtholz et al., 2002) were also used. Ocean heat content (OHC) in the Atlantic water layer was calculated with the reference temperature of 0°C and ocean heat content anomalies (independent of the selected reference temperature) were obtained as a difference between annual field and the long-term OHC mean (2000-2016).

Time series of temperature and salinity, and their normalized anomalies (that have been calculated by dividing the anomalies from the long-term mean by the standard deviation over the same reference period as for the long-term mean) have been calculated for the selected key locations along the poleward Atlantic inflow to follow transformation of Atlantic water on the way to the Arctic Ocean and its long-term spatial changes. The key sites for monitoring different branches of the Atlantic inflow were defined in the eastern Greenland Sea, in the Barents Sea Opening, in the southern and northern Fram Strait and north of Svalbard. For these locations, the averaged properties of Atlantic water (and other water masses) were calculated from standard sections over stations located in the Atlantic-origin flow.

A dedicated website of the AREX program is under preparation and in near future will provide access to all derived products obtained from over 20 years of in situ measurements in the studied domain. The foreseen products include long-term means, annual maps and their anomalies for ocean temperature and salinity at different depth levels and averaged in different water masses and depth intervals. For the water masses, the layer thickness and its upper and lower boundaries will be also provided. Estimates of ocean heat content (integrated over the entire domain and as spatial maps of the ocean heat content per unit area, representing the heat content in the unit water column) will be available for each annual survey. Time series of physical ocean properties in the key locations for the Atlantic water inflow and their long-term means and anomalies will be available based on measurements at the standard sections. In the future, the products initially derived from ship-based measurements will be also augmented with data collected with Argo floats, annually deployed by IOPAN in the Atlantic inflow domain. Selected examples of the ocean climate statistics based on the derived products from AREX measurements are presented below (subsections 2.1.1 and 2.1.2 and Figs. 1.1 – 1.12).

Spatial variability of different ocean variables and derived parameters is shown in Subsection 2.1.1. Exemplary long-term mean fields of temperature and salinity averaged in the Atlantic water layer, mean Atlantic water layer thickness, and relative ocean heat content per unit surface area are shown on Fig. 2.1 and illustrate the long-term mean ocean state in the Atlantic domain of the Nordic Seas and Fram Strait. Interannual (summer to summer) variability of large-scale fields in 1996-2020 is presented on Figs 2.2-2.7. These maps present derived integrative properties of the ocean, including annual distributions of mean temperature and salinity of Atlantic water (Figs 2.2 and 2.4), anomalies of mean AW temperature from the long-term mean (Fig. 2.3), AW layer thickness (Fig. 2.5), and relative ocean heat content (Fig. 2.6) and its anomalies from the long-term mean (Fig. 2.7). These derived properties allow for more integrative comparison between e.g., in situ observations and model results, or for obtaining more general information about physical background and its anomalies for environmental studies. In addition to derived integrative parameters, the website (in preparation) will include spatial fields of measured variables at different depth/pressure levels to allow for more direct comparison with e.g., model results.

In the following Subsection 2.2.1, selected long time series of temperature and salinity, measured at key locations for the Atlantic inflow towards the Arctic Ocean and averaged to best represent the AW layer and location of its core, are presented on Figs 2.9-2.12. The exemplary time series illustrate long-term changes in ocean climate observed in the eastern Norwegian Sea (before splitting of AW inflow between the Barents Sea and Fram Strait branches), southern Fram Strait (before main recirculation branches return part of Atlantic water westward and southward towards the North Atlantic), and northern Fram Strait (from where the Atlantic inflow joins the Arctic Ocean Boundary Current). Additionally, long-term changes in temperature and salinity of deep waters in the Greenland Sea are shown. All time series are presented as measured variables as well as

standardized anomalies which allows for direct comparison between different locations, water masses and depth levels.

2.1.1 Large-scale fields of temperature, salinity, and ocean heat content

Mean temperature and salinity of the Atlantic water layer, and the mean AW layer thickness and relative heat content are shown on Fig. 2.1. The lateral boundaries of the Atlantic inflow are distinctly visible in the temperature and salinity fields, while mean AW temperature and salinity decrease substantially during the northward flow due to atmospheric cooling and lateral exchange with less saline and colder water of Arctic origin, transported southward. Annual temperature and salinity fields shown on Figs 2.2. and 2.4 indicate strong interannual variability both in the spatial structure of the Atlantic origin inflow waters and their properties. In the first pentad, time series of mean AW properties at different sections and spatial maps of averaged properties show an increase of the AW temperature (with its maximum in 2006) accompanied by the increase of AW salinity, observed in the entire domain of the Atlantic inflow. During the following pentad AW temperature significantly decreased, in particular in Fram Strait, where the range of Atlantic water recirculating westward from the West Spitsbergen Current was also limited. After short-term decrease, AW salinity remained relatively high, and in some years (e.g. 2011 or 2014) it was close to the long-term maximum observed in 2006. Variability of the AW layer thickness was characterized by different pattern shown on Fig.2.5. During the maximum inflow of warm Atlantic waters, an increased thickness of the AW layer was observed only in the Norwegian Sea (the source region for the northern domain), while in the eastern Greenland Sea and Fram Strait, the lower boundary of AW was located at about 600 m. In the last 6-7 years, the AW thickness significantly increased in the entire Atlantic domain, reaching in 2014 maximum values of above 800m in the north-eastern Greenland Sea and Fram Strait.

Thickness of the Atlantic water layer is a key parameter for calculating ocean heat content in the studied region. However, it varies significantly on different time scales (from monthly to multiannual and decadal). Changes on weekly to monthly scales can result from short-period variability of the Atlantic water transport driven by atmospheric forcing and/or mesoscale structures like eddies or meanders, moving through the measured area. On longer time scales (multiannual and longer), changes in the AW layer thickness can be linked to increased inflow of warm and salty source waters from the North Atlantic, driven by long-term variations of the Subpolar Gyre intensity and extent. Since the ocean heat transport by the Atlantic inflow depends on water temperature, current velocity and layer thickness, amount of oceanic heat delivered to the Arctic Ocean is related to all parameters above. Schauer and Beszczynska-Möller (2009) showed from the measurements at the moored array in the northern Fram Strait that periods with the highest observed temperature of Atlantic water are not concurrent with the periods of maximum ocean heat transport to the Arctic Ocean.

Ocean heat content (OHC) is a derived quantity, integrating changes in temperature and layer thickness of Atlantic water. It is always calculated as relative heat content, referenced to the selected reference temperature (in the current study and this report Tref of 0°C is adopted). Spatial distributions of ocean heat content per unit surface area integrated in the Atlantic water layer (warmer than 0°C) are shown on Fig.2.6 and their anomalies from the long-term mean on Fig.2.7. A significant increase of ocean heat content was observed in the entire Atlantic inflow region in 2005 and 2006 in result of warm anomaly, propagating northward through the northern North Atlantic and Nordic Seas. However similarly high values of ocean heat content were found in the last pentad in the Atlantic water domain of the Norwegian and Greenland seas. Mean zonal ocean heat content in the Atlantic water layer decreases nearly twofold between 72°N and 80°N due to ocean-air-sea ice interactions and lateral exchanges at the boundaries with adjacent colder water masses. Mesoscale eddies play an important role by shedding from the main Atlantic water current and transporting warm and salty water towards the deep basins. Passings of mesoscale eddies can be noticed in time series of moored observations of temperature and currents (e.g. Schauer et al., 2003) and in the sections based on ship-borne oceanographic measurements (e.g. Walczowski, 2013). Only in recent years, the resolution of numerical models started to allow proper representation of mesoscale eddies and meanders generated by the Atlantic water flow (Wekerle et al. 2018; Crews et al., 2018).

Fig. 2.1 Long-term (2000-2016) mean spatial fields of the Atlantic water (a) temperature, (b) salinity, (c) layer thickness, and (d) relative ocean heat content based on in situ observations from the AREX program.

The highest values of OHC were observed in 2005-2006 and in the following years a decrease of ocean heat content was found until 2014. After 2014 total heat content in the Atlantic water domain significantly increased, reaching values close to those from mid-2000. Time series of the AW ocean heat content are similar for the whole AW layer (warmer than 0°C) and for its warm fraction (with temperature higher than 2°C), but relative mean temperatures and layer thickness show significant differences. A stable increase was found for the mean thickness of the Atlantic water layer with its highest values observed in the last pentad. In the period of strongest warm anomalies (2005-2006), AW layer thickness was relatively low while a significant rise of AW temperature resulted in the highest observed values of OHC in the entire AW domain. As opposite, an OHC increase in the last years resulted from a strong increase in the AW layer thickness and less dramatic increase of AW temperature. These differences can suggest different mechanisms and intensity of AW modification during its northward flow in different periods as well as indicate changes in the source water properties in the North Atlantic. An increased ocean heat content in the southern part of the Atlantic domain which is not reflected in the heat content in Fram Strait suggest an increased AW inflow through the Barents Sea Opening (BSO). Results obtained by other authors on the Barents Sea warming (Lind et al., 2018) and diminishing sea ice cover (Onarheim et al., 2018) confirm this conclusion.

Fig. 2.2 Spatial fields of vertically averaged temperature of the Atlantic water layer ($T > 0^{\circ}\text{C}$, $S > 34.92$) measured in June-July 2000-2016 during the AREX program.

Fig. 2.3 Spatial fields of anomalies from the long-term mean 2000-2016 of vertically averaged temperature of the Atlantic water layer ($T > 0^{\circ}\text{C}$, $S > 34.92$) measured in June-July in 2000-2016 during the AREX program.

Fig. 2.4 Spatial fields of vertically averaged salinity of the Atlantic water layer ($T > 0^{\circ}\text{C}$, $S > 34.92$) measured in June-July in 2000-2016 during the AREX program.

Fig. 2.5 Spatial fields of the Atlantic water ($T > 0^{\circ}\text{C}$, $S > 34.92$) layer thickness measured in June-July in 2000-2016 during the AREX program.

Fig. 2.6 Spatial fields of the Atlantic water ($T > 0^{\circ}\text{C}$, $S > 34.92$) ocean heat content measured in June-July in 2000-2016 during the AREX program.

Fig. 2.7 Spatial fields of ocean heat content anomalies in the Atlantic water layer, calculated with the reference to the long-term mean (2000–2016), obtained from in situ measurements collected in June–July 2000–2016 during the AREX program.

Relative ocean heat content per unit surface area (shown on Fig. 2.6) depends on temperature of water masses and layer thickness and can be integrated for the entire measured domain to obtain total ocean heat content in the selected layer (e.g. AW layer as shown on Fig. 2.8) or entire water column. This integrated quantity is an important parameter, describing ocean climate and can be used for calibration and validation of ocean models (as a better measure than temperature measured in a single point). While the relative ocean heat content depends on reference temperature, derived anomalies are independent of this parameter and give insight into spatial differences in changing ocean state, in particular ocean warming.

Fig. 2.8 (a) Domain averaged AW temperature and AW layer thickness, (b) domain integrated relative ocean heat content in AW, and (c) domain integrated relative ocean heat content in AW extended to 2020 calculated from the linear regression model based on three standard sections in the northern Greenland Sea, southern Fram Strait and northern Fram Strait.) Based on measurements in June-July in 2000-2016 during the AREX program.

2.1.2 Time series of physical ocean parameters at key locations (sections)

Among 8-10 sections regularly repeated during AREX summer surveys, three sections were selected as representative for different regimes of the Atlantic water poleward flow. Section K located along 75°N represents conditions in the eastern Greenland Sea, directly after splitting the Atlantic water current into the Barents Sea Branch entering through the Barents Sea Opening and Fram Strait Branch, continuing northward along the western Spitsbergen shelf break as the West Spitsbergen Current. Section N located at 76°30'N (west of Sørkapp) shows conditions typical for the southern Fram Strait before strong westward recirculation which further north removes a part of Atlantic water from the poleward flow and returns back towards the North Atlantic. Section EB2 along 78°50'N represents the inflow of Atlantic water already after losing some volume due to the recirculation and the remaining part continues north of Svalbard into the Arctic Ocean as a boundary current. Long-term time series of physical ocean variables at these sections are the bases for statistical analysis.

Fig. 2.9 Time series of (b) temperature, (c) normalized anomaly of temperature from the long-term mean, (d) salinity, and (e) normalized anomaly of salinity at the Eastern Greenland Sea section at 75°N averaged in 50-150 m between 10°E and 13°E (shown on (a)).

Time series of Atlantic water properties in the eastern Greenland Sea show the long-term variability of the Atlantic inflow in the Fram Strait Branch after a part of AW diverted into the Barents Sea Opening. The remaining flow of AW continues northward in the eastern Fram Strait thus it constitutes a source water for AW further modified in Fram Strait. The most pronounced features are maximum warming in 2005-2007 and higher than average temperature since 2012 while significantly increased salinity was found in the last decade.

Fig. 2.10 Time series of (b) temperature, (c) normalized anomaly of temperature from the long-term mean, (d) salinity, and (e) normalized anomaly of salinity at the southern Fram Strait section at 76°30'N at 200 m between 9°E and 12°E (shown on (a)).

Atlantic water at 76°30'N in the southern Fram Strait shows similar pattern of temporal variability as in the upstream region in the Greenland Sea with maximum temperature in 2005-2007 and periods of relatively warm conditions in the last decade. Higher than average salinity has been observed for the long period between 2005 and 2017 albeit its significant decrease was observed in the last two years. For the last decade temperature and salinity time series mostly showed decoupled variability except last two years when both parameters dropped.

Fig. 2.11 Time series of (b) temperature, (c) normalized anomaly of temperature from the long-term mean, (d) salinity, and (e) normalized anomaly of salinity at the northern Fram Strait section at 78°50'N averaged in 50-500 m between 5°E and 9°E (shown on (a)).

Time series of Atlantic water properties at 78°50'N in the northern Fram Strait were extended backward using the AWI data collected during ship campaigns in Fram Strait. Strong recirculation during the Atlantic water passage along the shelf break west of Svalbard significantly modifies properties of the Atlantic inflow. Temperature maxima in 2006-2007 are still outstanding but after this period strong interannual variations are observed with a period of a few years. Except the strongest events there is little coherence between measurements at different sections in Fram Strait what highlights mechanisms of AW modifications on the way northward. AW properties in the inflow core at this section represent source water for the Arctic Ocean Boundary Current as the majority of WSC core will continue around north-west corner of Svalbard and further eastward, bringing ocean heat into the Arctic.

Fig. 2.12 Time series of (b) temperature, (c) normalized anomaly of temperature from the long-term mean, (d) salinity, and (e) normalized anomaly of salinity in the deep waters of the eastern Greenland Sea at the section at 75°N at 3000 m at 5°E (shown on (a)).

2.2 Ocean variability from year-round measurements on moorings north of Svalbard

IOPAN contributed to the moored observatory north of Svalbard with two moorings dedicated to measurements of physical ocean properties and sea ice in the key region of Atlantic water inflow to the Arctic Ocean in 2017-2020. One mooring (IOPAS1x, where x stands for the deployment number) was deployed at the INTAROS line at 22°E over the upper continental slope at the water depth of 850 m. The second mooring, labeled IOPAS2x (x for the deployment number) was deployed as a part of the A-TWAIN mooring line along 31°E over the mid-slope at the depth of 1200 m and complemented Norwegian moorings deployed in the frame of the A-TWAIN/Nansen legacy projects.

Fig. 2.13 Positions of IOPAN moorings north of Svalbard deployed in 2012-2019.

The IOPAN mooring measurements during INTAROS comprised three deployment periods, including the pilot phase (2017-2018), the first fieldwork period (2018-2019), and the second fieldwork period (2019-2020). The first two deployments (2017-2018 and 2018-2019) and specifications of instruments and measured variables are described in detail in the deliverable D3.7 while the last deployment (2019-2020) is described in the deliverable D.3.11.

INTAROS moorings deployed in 2017-2020 were continuation of the IOPAN moorings, operated since 2012 as a part of the A-TWAIN array at 31°E (and the additional upstream mooring at 22°E as a precursor of the INTAROS array). Summary of IOPAN mooring deployments north of Svalbard is provided in Table 1.1.

Table 2.1 Deployment periods and positions of IOPAN moorings north of Svalbard

Mooring ID	Water depth	Deployment date	Recovery date	Latitude decimal deg	Longitude decimal deg
A-TWAIN moorings (2012-2017)					
IOPAS5	3310 m	24.09.2012	19.09.2013	81.97402	29.88033
IOPAS6	855 m	25.09.2012	20.09.2013	81.49018	22.00418
IOPAS4	2081 m	24.09.2013	16.09.2015	81.63130	30.66617
IOPAS6b	1020 m	17.08.2014	15.09.2015	80.74416	15.90483
IOPAS7	1210 m	20.09.2015	18.09.2017	81.57530	30.00592
INTAROS moorings (2017-2020)					
IOPAS11	854 m	22.09.2017	04.08.2018	81.48978	22.00383
IOPAS21	1210 m	21.09.2017	04.08.2018	81.57513	31.00502
IOPAS12	861 m	11.08.2018	06.09.2019	81.48649	21.99268
IOPAS22	1228 m	09.08.2018	19.11.2019	81.57481	30.99217
IOPAS13	855 m	24.11.2019	24.10.2020	81.48605	21.93773
NERSC4	3458 m	05.09.2019	24.07.2020	81.78490	22.00470

2.2.1 Preliminary statistics of physical ocean properties and derived parameters

From available measurements collected on different moorings in the key location north of Svalbard, long-term time series of essential ocean physical variables were compiled, based on collocated moorings. The best example is represented by the mooring located at the INTAROS line along 22°E, at the water depth of approx. 850m, which was deployed for four year-long periods in 2012-2013, 2017-2018, 2018-2019, and 2019-2020. Temporal variability of temperature and derived parameters (e.g. relative ocean heat content) at the IOPAN mooring at 22°E and their basic statistics are presented below on Figs 2.14-2.18. For comparison Fig. 2.19 shows temperature evolution in the upper 850m at the IOPAN mooring at 31°E (A-TWAIN line) in 2015-2017. Mean profiles of temperature measured in four deployment years (Fig.2.14) reveal significant interannual variability in the vertical structure of Atlantic water layer which is most pronounced in the upper 300-400 m. There are also clear differences in the AW temperature ranges at different depths in different years.

Fig. 2.14 Temperature profiles (grey lines), their means (red solid line) and standard deviations (red dashed line) measured at the IOPAN mooring at 22°E (INTAROS line) at the water depth of 850 m in (a) 2012-2013, (b) in 2017-2018, (c) 2018-2019, and (d) 2019-2020.

Fig. 2.15 Monthly (January to December) temperature profiles (grey lines), their means (red solid line) and standard deviations (red dashed line) measured at the IOPAN mooring at 22°E (INTAROS line) at the water depth of 850 m in 2017-2020.

Fig. 2.16 Annual cycle (long-term monthly means) of temperature averaged in seven layers of 100 m thickness measured at the IOPAN mooring at 22°E (INTAROS line) in 2012-2013 and 2017-2020. Long-term mean annual cycle in the entire measured water column (50-750m) is shown by the dashed black line.

Fig. 2.17 (a) Sea surface temperature (SST) and ice concentration (IC) from the OISST v2 at the mooring location, (b) Temperature evolution in the water column between 50 and 830 m in 2017-2020 measured at the IOPAN mooring at 22°E (INTAROS line), (c) temperature averaged in the layer 80-200 m and 80-600m, (d) relative ocean heat content (OHC) in the upper layer 80-200 m (daily values and 30-day means), and (e) daily and 30-day averaged ocean heat content change (dOHC) in the 80-200 m layer.

Fig. 2.18 (a) Sea surface temperature (SST) and ice concentration (IC) from the OISST v2 at the mooring location, (b) temperature evolution in the water column between 50 and 750 m, and (c) temperature profiles measured in 2012-2013 at the IOPAN mooring at 22°E (INTAROS line).

Fig. 2.19 (a) Temperature evolution in the water column between 50 and 850 m and (b) temperature profiles (grey lines), their mean (red solid line) and standard deviation (red dashed line) measured at the IOPAN mooring at 31°E (A-TWAIN line) in 2015-2017.

2.3 Sea ice statistics in the region of mooring measurements from satellite observations

For the analysis of time series of physical ocean properties measured during ship-based surveys and on oceanographic moorings, basic sea ice statistics were calculated for the key region north of Svalbard where the impact of Atlantic water inflow is most profound. Time series and averaged spatial maps of sea ice concentration (SIC) were obtained from two remote sensing products, and SSM/I Sea Ice Concentration Monthly 25 km (Comiso et al., 2015) MASAM2 Daily 4 km Arctic Sea Ice Concentration (Fetterer et al., 2015). Main statistics of the averaged sea ice concentration were calculated for two regions, one north-west of Svalbard where Atlantic inflow enters the Arctic Ocean Boundary Current and one north-east of Svalbard where both moored arrays (INTAROS and A-TWAIN) are located (Fig. 2.20).

Fig. 2.20 Location of two regions, north-west of Svalbard (NSw) and north-east of Svalbard (NSE) for which time series of averaged sea ice concentration were calculated from SSM/I (1996-2020) and MASAM2 (2012-2020).

Mean 1996-2020 sea ice concentration (SIC)

Mean 1996-2020 winter (DJFM) SIC

Mean 1996-2020 spring-summer (AMJJ) SIC

Mean annual winter (DJFM) SIC

Winter 1996

Mean annual spring-summer (AMJJ) SIC

Spring-Summer 1996

Winter 1997

Spring-Summer 1997

Winter 1998

Spring-Summer 1998

Fig. 2.21 Spatial maps of long-term annual, long-term seasonal and monthly averaged sea ice concentration calculated from SSM/I data for the region north of Svalbard for 1996-2020.

Fig. 2.22 Time series for monthly averaged sea ice concentration in 1996-2020 from SSM/I data for the region north-west of Svalbard (NS_w shown on Fig. 2.20).

Fig. 2.23 Time series for monthly averaged sea ice concentration in 1996-2020 from SSM/I data for the region north-east of Svalbard (NSE shown on Fig. 2.20).

b)

Fig. 2.24 (a) Long-term averaged monthly means of sea ice concentration (black line), individual monthly means (color points) and their standard deviation (dashed black line) and (b) monthly anomalies of sea ice concentrations from mean annual cycle in 1996-2020 from SSM/I data for the region north-west of Svalbard (NS_w shown on Fig. 2.20).

a)

b)

Fig. 2.25 (a) Long-term averaged monthly means of sea ice concentration (black line), individual monthly means (color points) and their standard deviation (dashed black line) and (b) monthly anomalies of sea ice concentrations from mean annual cycle 1996-2020 from SSM/I data for the region north-east of Svalbard (NS_E shown on Fig. 2.20).

2.4 Summary and outlook

In Section 2 we presented the selected data products obtained from in situ measurements during ship-based repeated observational campaigns and fixed ocean moorings, supported by auxiliary information about sea ice conditions related to collected ocean measurements, obtained from remote sensing products. The main goal of these activities is to prepare the collection of data products, representing ocean and sea ice statistics based on long time series of available measurements that illustrate the mean state and variability of the ocean in the selected regions and key locations in the integrative way. Integrated or averaged properties are better suited for different applications (like e.g. calibration/validation of numerical ocean models) than a single time series in one location since they are less prone to errors and inaccuracies resulting from using a single point measurement and trying to compare observed and modelled quantities "one-to-one".

The overarching aim is to establish a dedicated website where all long-term spatial fields and time series, including their statistics, will be presented as visual information (graphic files) and as digital information (e.g., netCDF data files). These products will be publicly available to all stakeholders and if a data product is not available (but can be obtained from available observations), it will be generated on demand via a user's feedback mechanism, implemented on the website (e.g. spatial distributions at different depths level or vertical averages over a specified depth range). In the final version, the required derived parameters should be calculated automatically via a set of dedicated scripts. Collection of data products derived from in situ measurements will be extended as new data are available. For example, sea ice draft and drift measurements were collected at the selected INTAROS moorings in 2017-2020 concurrently with other ocean variables but

their processing has not been yet finished. When available, they will be used to calculate other parameters (as ice thickness, ice transport, etc.) which will be visualized on the website.

A full ambition is to complement in situ data sets (spatial fields, time series, statistics) with auxiliary data from external sources, already preprocessed to represent the measurement location or area. The sea level pressure, wind stress and wind curl, wind vectors at 10 m, air temperature at 2 m, sensible and latent heat fluxes and short- and longwave radiation will be retrieved from the most updated reanalysis (currently ERA5) for the representative region of each presented in situ time series. Different sea ice products from remote sensing, including not only ice concentration but also ice thickness, ice drift and location of ice edge will be extracted for mooring locations and areas of ship-borne measurements to establish multiparameter data collection for e.g. studies of ocean-sea ice-atmospheric interactions. Last but not least, statistics obtained from in situ data sets presented here will be compared to available climatologies to evaluate their error in the studied region or location.

The ocean and ice statistics presented here will be also used as an input to ocean climate state assessments (e.g. ICES Report on Ocean Climate; e.g. Gonzales-Pola et al., 2019) or environmental assessments which require background information about changes in physical environment. Finally, the obtained data products will be exploited in the planned scientific publications which are currently under preparations for the INTAROS Special Issue in Ocean Science or the Copernicus Earth System Science Data journal. Presented time series, spatial maps and their statistics will also be used in a PhD dissertation by the INTAROS PhD student who is co-author of this report.

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3 THE ACOUSTIC ENVIRONMENT IN THE FRAM STRAIT.

The regional variability of ‘ocean sound’ levels influence the living conditions for marine life, but also our capability to use acoustic methodology to observe the water column and sea floor as well as the possibility to communicate underwater. The acoustic environments are described by the natural generation of sound (e.g. mammals, waves, sea ice processes), the sound produced by human activity (e.g. seismic, ice breakers, shipping, research instrumentation) and how the sound is propagating after it is generated. The acoustic propagation is strongly dependent on the highly variable ice-ocean environment e.g. water-mass stratification, sea ice conditions, wind, ocean waves, bathymetry, and the geo-acoustic properties of the sea floor. How the acoustic signal interacts with the sea ice and how it reacts to the oceanographic stratification and variability depends strongly on the frequency of the signal. Knowledge about the ocean and the sea ice is essential to understand the variability in the acoustic environment between different regions and seasons in the Arctic.

The climate induced environmental changes in the Arctic will change both the mechanisms and processes producing natural ocean sound, and how the sound propagates. Increased accessibility and thereby traffic to the Arctic region will change the amount of sound produced by human activities. The changes will be of different characters in different regions of the Arctic, but in this report, we will primarily address the marginal ice zones of the Fram Strait. To assess the effect of the changes in the Arctic it is important to benchmark the current state of the Arctic acoustic environments and make recommendations for future observing system. Acoustic multipurpose network offers improved observing capability of ocean sound and mean ocean temperature, as well as facilitating for improved observing capacity using floats and gliders (e.g. Mikhalevsky et al 2015, Howe et al. 2019, Lee et al. 2019).

In the following we present some of the history of acoustic investigation in the Eastern Arctic, which is by far not complete as it is focused on the work performed by NERSC and collaborators. Furthermore, we provide an assessment of more recent acoustic observing systems in the Arctic using the ARCMAP database. In the remaining of the report, we focus on the analysis of the UNDER-ICE data set. Note that in passive acoustics ‘ocean sound’ is more commonly used today, while ambient noise was more common to use in the 80s and 90s. The measurement/observation method, however, is the same: recording of the sound in the ocean. The term ‘ocean sound scape’ is also used, but it is more diffuse, and we will not use it in this report.

3.1 Ambient noise Experiments in the Fram Strait and Barents Sea

In the 80s and early 90s several acoustic experiments were carried out in the marginal ice zones of the Barents Sea and the Fram strait. The experiments were multi disciplinary and several ships and aircrafts were used to collect data (e.g. Johannessen et al. 2003).

As part of the Marginal Ice Zone Experiment – MIZEX campaigns in 83,84,85, 87 and SIZEX (Seasonal Ice Zone Experiment) 89 and 92 several ambient noise experiments were carried out. Several sonobuoys were dopped in 100 times 100 kilometers areas in the Marginal Ice Zone in the Fram Strait and the Barents Sea. In some cases, Airborne XBTs were dropped to know about the temperature stratification of the ocean. The recordings were sent via radio link to the aircraft which could record up to 16 channels simultaneously. A known calibration signal was sent through the recording system to ensure correct levels in the analysis. A particular focus of the investigations was to study how the ambient noise were generated and how the ambient noise characteristics varied within the ice edge area with different ice edge configuration in areas with ice edge eddies. It was found significant hotspots within the convergence zones related to ice edge eddies and in cases when swell and waves were propagating towards a compact ice edge. Other findings were that in grease ice areas the ambient noise levels were much lower than inside the ice edge and in open ocean. Furthermore, grounded icebergs in the Barents Sea were “cutting” up the ice field due to strong tidal current, and thereby producing a lot of noise. The results from these studies were presented in Sagen, 1998 and in Johannessen et al. 2003. In the period from 2010-2012 four aircraft missions were carried out in the Fram Strait and the Barents Sea (Sagen et al. 2014, Sagen and Tollefsen, 2014; and Tollefsen 2016). In Figure 3.1 all the different aircraft missions from 1989 are shown. A significant difference from the 1980s and 1990s were that there was significant contribution to the ‘ocean sound’ from seismic exploration in the North Sea and Barents Sea.

As part of UNDER-ICE and WIFAR project a drifting acoustic station provided acoustic data from the Marginal Ice Zone in 2012, 2013. These were analyzed in Geyer et al. 2016 to observe the impact of ice breaker operating in the MIZ area and from seismic investigations.

Figure 3.1. Overview of ambient noise experiments using sonobuoy drops from Norwegian P3 aircrafts in the 80s, 90s and in the period from 2010-2012. (Figure by Marcus Pira and Kristine Øxnevad Larsen, Bachelor students at UiB). These experiments were carried out together with the Norwegian Defence Research Establishment (Johannessen et al. 2003, Tollefsen et al. 2014, 2016, Sagen et al. 2014).

3.2 The evolution from acoustic propagation studies to multipurpose acoustic systems.

3.2.1 Acoustic propagation experiments in Eastern Arctic.

During MIZEX 84 a ship-to-ship transmission study were carried out using frequencies from 20 Hz to 200 Hz. The ranges studied were up to 100 km and the path was partly covered by sea ice. The objective was to study the Doppler shift and fluctuations around the shifts. The study showed that eddies and other mesoscale motions are important in understanding the acoustic fluctuations in the Marginal Ice Zone (MIZ) (Dyer et al. 1987). Following up MIZEX 84 experiment a numerical study using oceanographical data from MIZEX 84 as input to ray tracing and parabolic approximation codes was carried out. The study did not include reflections from bottom or surface. The study showed that the low frequency sound is generally refracted below the depth of the receivers due to the warmer water associated with the eddies in the Fram Strait. The numerical results indicated that eddies could affect propagation loss, and that 1 kHz yields a loss more than 20 dB smaller than at 50 Hz (Mellberg et al 1987). Using the same approach propagation of 50 Hz signals through a frontal zone were studied. It was found that the propagation loss and the modal structure in a Frontal zone are very sensitive to source and receiver configuration. A frontal zone can increase the loss by 20 dB over a distance less than 10 km (Mellberg et al. 1991), this was confirmed by another study using 3D modelling (Heathershaw et al. 1991).

During SIZEX 92 sound propagation experiments were carried out in the Barents Sea dropping sonobuoys and SUS charges in the marginal ice zone. In this region the water depth is between 200-300 meters. The bottom is described as bed rock with 40 % covered with sandy gravel. CTD section and AXBT drops show that there is a 50-80-meter-deep surface channel outside the ice edge, while crossing into the ice-covered area the channel is deepening to 100 m. Five desensitized sonobuoys were deployed by aircraft in open sea, at the ice edge, and within the ice edge. Thereafter, around 20 SUS charges were dropped at different locations across the ice

edge, and the broadband sound were recorded at the sonobuoys. While the transmission loss in the deep Arctic follows the of cylindrical spreading the losses (Diachoke, 1976) the study in SIZEX 92 region show that the transmission loss in the shallow Barents Sea follows a spreading law close to or stronger than the spherical spreading. The strong losses are generally due to geometrical losses, including reflection losses due to bottom interaction, while the scattering from the ice cover seems to be less or equal to the scattering from ice depending on frequency. Using the observations, the scattering above 100 Hz seems to be less in this region than in the interior Arctic, while below 100 Hz the scattering is similar or higher than the scattering in the interior Arctic. During the EU project Acoustic Monitoring of the Arctic Ocean Climate (AMOC) (1998-2001) numerical simulations with climate modelling results were used to study the acoustic sensitivity to ocean climate change in the Fram Strait and in the interior Arctic. This project laid the ground for the future work towards implementation of acoustic thermometry experiments in the Fram Strait. The result of the study are reported in Johannessen et al. 2001, and in the following we summarize the main results.

Based on the numerical study it was recommended that propagation paths between source and receiver should avoid shelf areas and other and regions with water depths shallower than 1500 m. AMOC results indicated that sufficient signal to noise ratio, which does not require post processing, can be achieved by using a transmission level of 160 dB in Fram strait and 180 - 195 db in the interior of the Arctic, depending on frequency and ranges. Deployment depth of source is a crucial factor for successful transmission. In the Arctic Basin relevant source deployment depths should be at 500 m or deeper to capture mode 2 and 3 waves propagation through the Atlantic water masses. The results suggest that shallow source deployment in the upper water masses will not capture the expected warming of the Atlantic water as it was predicted by the climate model simulations.

For the Fram Strait the simulations indicated that both a deep and a shallow source will provide information about the mean temperature of the water masses. A deep source gives the best results for long term monitoring of the climate, while the shallow source will provide information about the seasonal changes in the upper water masses. Due to strong mesoscale eddy activity in the Fram Strait, it can be difficult to separate arrival times of the different rays for every transmission. However, the simulations show that there are enough deep going rays which can be recognized to observe long-term changes in mean ocean temperature. Basin wide 20 Hz can be used for with minimum influence of sea ice, while in the Fram strait it is possible to use higher frequencies, especially in the ice-free part (West-Spitzbergen Current).

3.2.2 Implementation of multipurpose acoustic networks in the Arctic.

The evolution and integration of acoustic networks in an integrated Arctic Ocean Observing System is described in Figure 3.2, and Mikhalevesky et al. 2015, Howe et al. 2019, Worcester et al. 2021. In this report we describe the development of such systems in the Fram Strait.

DAMOCLES experiment in 2008-2009 two moorings were deployed in the central Fram Strait to pilot an acoustic thermometry. During this experiment a Webb source at 400 m transmitted 60 s long sweep (200-300 Hz) every 3 hours for a whole year. The receiver mooring had two four element arrays controlled by STAR technology developed at Scripps Institution of Oceanography. The system was programmed to receive the signal on 4 hydrophones spaced with 9 meters. The technology was limited to four hydrophones. The experiment is described in several reports and papers (e.g. Dushaw et al. 2016, 2017 and Sagen et al. 2017). The main acoustic propagation result from this work is that the environment in the West Spitsbergen is very little dispersive and it is hard to separate out different waterborne arrivals during this experiment. The arrivals are very much influenced by meso scale variability, and scattering effects from small scale variability makes the sound to sense the whole water column in an integrated way. This was used to develop an inversion technique to obtain the depth-range averaged sound speed and the corresponding ocean temperature (Dushaw et al 2017). The effect of salinity was shown to be below the noise level (Dushaw et al. 2016).

The DAMOCLES acoustic thermometry experiment was followed by implementation of the first multipurpose acoustic experiment in the Arctic as part of the EU project ACOBAR. This system built on the same source technology and STAR technology used in the DAMOCLES experiment. The system consisted of three source/receiver moorings in a triangle with a stand alone two four element hydrophone arrays in the middle. This experiment was designed to transmit two-way along three sections and one way from each source to the receiver in the middle. The sources were programmed to transmit the tomographic broadband signal every three hours and to transmit RAFOS signal every 6 hours in given periods to facilitate for glider navigation. The receivers were programmed to listen for the 90 s long signal, but they also provided shorter periods with no signals for ambient noise. Each receiver array in the source moorings comprised 4 hydrophones separated

by 9 meters. The stand-alone receiver moorings had two arrays tail-by-tail with a total of 8 hydrophones. During ACOBAR a short portion of time the westernmost sections were covered with ice. More, details can be found in Sagen et al. 2017, Geyer et al. 2020. Inverted ocean temperature from ACOBAR and DAMOCLES have been processed and published (Dushaw 2017, Geyer et al 2021).

ACOBAR was followed by the UNDER-ICE project funded by the Research Council of Norway. During this experiment 5 moorings were deployed in the Fram Strait from 2010 to 2012 which gave 8 source-receiver sections. The moorings were equipped with new receiver technology allowing for many more hydrophones, and in our case, we used 10 hydrophones. Several source-receiver sections were covered with ice during the whole experiment period. The data from this experiment has been processed and analysed in INTAROS and in a ONR project, and the work are submitted as proceedings to POMA with editorial review. Extensions of the papers forms the basis of the remaining of the report.

INTAROS has contributed towards the development of standards for data and meta data, and improved data processing methodologies. However, there are several steps left in the development of efficient and operational data processing as well as applications and services benefiting from the possibilities offered by the system e.g. development of robust methods for geo-positioning in floats and gliders. Multipurpose acoustic networks are promoted as important infra structure contribution to an integrated Arctic Ocean observing system (e.g. n Mikhalevsky et al. 2015, Worcester et al. 2020. Lee et al. 2019). See Figure 3.2. Our activity in the Fram Strait has led to the implementation of a basin wide acoustic thermometry experiment which have shown that technology used in acoustic networks are at the technical readiness level (TRL) 7. Some information about this system is provided to D3.13.

The Evolution of Multipurpose acoustic networks in the Arctic

Figure 3.2. The evolution of multipurpose acoustic networks in the Arctic from feasibility of trans Arctic transmissions with heavy equipment (1994,1999), development and implementation of regional networks in the Fram Strait (2008-2016) and Beaufort Sea (2016/2017), formulation of a vision for a trans Arctic system, and implementation of a pilot system using modern technology in the Coordinated Arctic Acoustic Thermometry Experiment (2019-2020).

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4 ANALYSIS OF PASSIVE ACOUSTIC IN SITU OBSERVING SYSTEMS IN THE ARCTIC OCEAN USING ARCMAP

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Figure numbers are Figure 1-10.

Abstract of submitted POMA paper: The Integrated Arctic Observing System project has conducted a survey of Arctic in situ observing systems, in situ and remote sensing data collections. Based on questionnaires from this survey we have developed ARCMAP (<https://arcmap.nersc.no>), a user-friendly web system for collecting and maintaining information about Arctic in situ observing systems and data collections. The information is stored in a database allowing easy generation of statistics, for example on spatial and temporal coverage, parameters observed and targeted application areas, nationality of owners, funding sources and periods and maturity of data storage and management. We have extracted information about systems observing ocean sound and located in the Arctic. We also compared with other repositories of metadata for acoustic observing systems. The ARCMAP database currently has 11 occurrences of systems containing ocean sound and provides assessment information, e.g. on data storage, in addition to basic metadata, e.g. location and time coverage. This study focuses on sustainability of the observing systems, and it is found that the typical system is focused, project based, funded at the national level and has non-advanced routines for data storage and management, in good agreement with the common view about Arctic observing systems.

4.1 Introduction

Sound is important for many marine animals in their communication, for predator and prey detection, and for some like the odontocete whales, echolocation is important. The Arctic is an important habitat for many marine animal species utilizing sound. The region is experiencing rapid change, with an overall decrease in sea ice extent during the last decades as the most prominent manifestation (PAME, 2019). The increased accessibility caused by opening up the Arctic may potentially intensify underwater noise due to commercial vessels, fishing, community re-supply, mining, tourist and pleasure craft traffic, military exercises and oil and gas extraction activities (seismic air guns, drilling, and construction). A comprehensive overview of baseline passive acoustic data is therefore needed as a reference for future studies of change in the acoustic environment in the Arctic. Furthermore, the Arctic is relatively little investigated in general and largely acoustically pristine, so more research efforts are needed. The comparably fewer observations and observation programs in the Arctic than elsewhere is mainly due to the harsh logistical conditions. In addition, observations are mostly process oriented, based on project funding, thus making them heterogeneous and largely unavailable outside the research community. In this regard it is positive that ocean sound has now become a mature Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) essential ocean variable (Howe et al., 2019).

In order to improve and augment the monitoring of the Arctic ocean and upon which decisions can be taken, there is a need for an extensive, harmonized and sustainable acoustic observation network. Presently, the observing systems are scattered and utilize different standards (IQOE, 2021). Howe et al. (2019) recommend that multipurpose acoustic systems be brought into operational status for monitoring the polar seas.

Information about existing observing systems in the Arctic, including passive acoustic networks, is scattered among multiple databases and websites. Therefore, we developed ARCMAP which is a user-friendly web system for collecting and maintaining information about Arctic in situ observing systems and data collections. A number of relevant metadata- and databases already exist, all with their specific purposes. A unique feature of ARCMAP is its focus on information regarding sustainability of the observing systems. For a selection of meta-databases we have performed a simple assessment with an aim to determine their capabilities with regard to acoustic observations (Section 6.2).

ARCMAP was developed as a contribution to the EU Horizon 2020 project Integrated Arctic Observing System (INTAROS), whose aim is to create a roadmap towards implementation of an integrated Arctic observing system (Tjernström et al., 2020). The present development (Section 6.3) may thus be seen as a stepping-stone on the road towards a complete delivery system for acoustic data in the Arctic. The major part

of this work provides an example of extraction of and interpretation of information from ARCMAP with regard to ocean sound. Through a search in the database for systems having Ocean sound as an observation parameter, records were extracted for further analysis, as described in Section 6.4. The results are discussed in Section 6.5, overall conclusions summarised in Section 6.6, and plans for exploitation outlined in Section 6.7.

4.2 Brief review of selected metadata and data systems

There exist a few websites for viewing metadata on acoustic observing systems that we are aware of. We follow the definitions of Tjernström et al. (2020): “An in-situ observing system consists of a data collection component (infrastructure) and a data management component (e-infrastructure). The data collection component is comprised of multiple sensors either belonging to a common fixed platform (such as cabled system, sea floor installation, mooring), which can be a single unit or a collection of units forming a network, or installed on a non-stationary platform (ship, aircraft, gliders, floats, ice buoys) [...]” In Table 1 we list some key information on four in-situ observing systems including ARCMAP (the latter presented in detail in Section 6.3).

The International Quiet Ocean Experiment (**IQOE**) website provides a menu point ‘Acoustic observing systems’ providing the user with a simple to use interface for getting an overview of passive acoustic monitoring sites Worldwide. The user has the option to select display of either autonomous or cabled systems. Then one can select up to 24 different information fields that are mostly of type free text. The results are then displayed in a table. No other filtering or export options are available.

Table 1 Overview of sites holding information of acoustic observing systems. i) as of 23 August 2021. ii) in addition, there are 2-3 fields per observed variable. iii) counting all observing systems. iv) 14 are of type text, 26 of type single or multiple choice. v) 115 systems in total, 11 systems observing ocean sound.

Site	URL	Area	Discipline theme /	No. of information fields	No. of systems ⁱ
IQOE	https://www.iqoe.org/systems	Global	Acoustics	24	109
CAFF PAM	https://geokart.npolar.no/Html5Viewer/index.html?viewer=ArcticPAM	Arctic	Acoustics	19	339
SIOS	https://sios-svalbard.org/sios-ri-catalogue	Svalbard	All themes	12 ⁱⁱ	261 ⁱⁱⁱ
ARCMAP	https://arcmmap.nersc.no	Arctic	All themes	47 ^{iv}	115/11 ^v

The Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna (**CAFF**) working group under Arctic Council leads a program on Pan-Arctic Passive Acoustic Monitoring (PAM). The CAFF PAM Metadata Database hosted by the Norwegian Polar Institute contains records of Passive Acoustic Monitoring (PAM) instruments deployed across the Arctic. A handy Graphical User Interface (GUI) allows zooming in on a map and selecting locations of interest. Multiyear and one-year sites are marked with separate colors. The subsequent table that is generated displays 19 fields, of which the majority contains text. Filtering and export options with a large flexibility for the user is implemented.

Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System (**SIOS**) maintains an Observation Facilities Catalogue holds observation facilities (i.e. instruments or collections thereof) collecting data on and near Svalbard. The description of observing systems follows the WMO standards as far as possible, in order to make entries unambiguous and interoperable internationally. A GUI facilitates the search operation, allowing for queries combining multiple criteria, among others, facility name, institution, project, and observed variable. Searching for ‘ocean sound’ or ‘ambient noise’ yields a few hits, which may imply that few acoustic observing systems in fjords and coastal regions of Svalbard have been registered so far.

ARCMAP maintains a database of in situ observing systems across multiple spheres (e.g. sea ice, ocean land, atmosphere) in the Arctic. We note that ARCMAP holds several information fields on assessment information that the other systems do not, therefore it has the highest number (47) for this parameter (Table 6.1).

For completeness we also include some widely used sites for data delivery, as data sampled by the observing systems should after processing and quality control be published in an open data repository.

[PANGAEA](#) is a database with global coverage currently holding more than 400,000 datasets from all disciplinary themes. However, selecting the ocean theme and searching for ‘sound’ yields only 221 results and does not seem to discern between active and passive acoustics, phrases as ‘sound velocity’, ‘echo sounder’ and location descriptions containing ‘sound’ in a name. Limiting the search by such phrases (preceding a string by a minus sign ‘-’, reduces the number of hits, but a universal way to isolate only passive acoustic measurements was not found. On the other hand, searching for ‘soundscape’ yields 20 unique hits.

The Norwegian Marine Data Center ([NMDC](#)) holds information on or links to marine datasets provided by mainly Norwegian institutions with emphasis on Norwegian waters, including Svalbard. A free search on ‘acoustic’ yields 81 hits, including echo sounder, sonar and ADCP measurements, whereas ‘ambient noise’ yields 6 data sets.

The [INTAROS Data Catalog](#) is a metadata catalog on Arctic datasets covering all disciplinary themes currently holding 137 datasets generated by the INTAROS project. A search yields 5 data sets tagged with ‘passive acoustics’ of which 4 also are tagged ‘ambient sound’.

[EMODNET](#) has for each of seven disciplinary themes, created a gateway to a range of data archives managed by a number of international data providing organisations. Selecting the physics theme and ‘underwater noise’ yields four hits only. For the biology theme a free search for ‘acoustic’ or ‘sound’ yielded 17 or 18 hits, respectively, with minor overlaps. The majority were recordings of mammal sound, but also some data sets dealt with active acoustics.

The Norwegian Polar Data Centre ([NPDC](#)) hosts data of the Norwegian Polar Institute from the Arctic and Antarctic. Free searches for ‘acoustic’, ‘sound’ or ‘noise’ yields 10, 14 and 3 hits, respectively (out of 260 total). Again, a large fraction consists of active acoustics and also non-marine data sets.

IQOE also provides an [Acoustic Data Portal](#) linking to 13 national or project sites holding passive acoustic data, of which several also contain general ocean data. To survey all those is beyond the scope of the present paper.

The [SIOS Data Portal](#) links to 83006 datasets. A search for ‘acoustic’ or ‘sound’ yields 12 and 10 hits, respectively, mostly for data dealing with active acoustics.

The Open Portal to Underwater Sound ([OPUS](#)) is under development by the Alfred Wegener Institute (IQOE, 2020). According to the information on the site “[t]he portal will give access to HAFOS, FRAM and PALAOA recordings by audio and synchronized spectral visualizations at staggered temporal resolution to enjoy underwater (night-)life”.

Summarizing, we have found that, except for the dedicated sound sites IQOE and CAFF, none of the data or metadata bases utilize ‘ocean sound’ as a keyword or observed variable. ARCMAP, as a recent development, has implemented it, and searches for this essential ocean variable thus become straightforward and yield unambiguous results. Our exploratory searches in selected data systems indicated that only a relatively small fraction of datasets on passive acoustics has been published in these open data bases. Further effort is therefore needed to advance production chains ensuring increased availability of passive acoustic data for science, public and private sector.

4.3 Design of ARCMAP

The INTAROS project has conducted a survey of Arctic in situ observing systems, in situ and remote sensing data collections (Tjernstrøm et al., 2020). Based on the questionnaires from this survey we have developed a user-friendly web system for collecting and maintaining information about Arctic in situ observing systems and data collections. This system, named ARCMAP, has been developed with support from INTAROS and the “Marine data in the Arctic: From mapping to knowledge” project funded by the Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment.

ARCMAP enables users to register and maintain information about Arctic in situ observing systems and data collections. The information is stored in a database allowing easy generation of statistics, for example spatial

and temporal coverage, parameters observed and targeted application areas, nationality of owners, funding sources and periods, maturity of data management.

The ARCMAP web site. <https://arcmmap.nersc.no/>, consists of three sub-sites: (1) A survey site for users to enter and update information on their assessed systems, (2) a client site where registered users can view and extract data about the assessed systems, (3) a statistics site generating plots on a daily basis, such as histograms of number of systems for various application areas, each for atmosphere, ocean and land, respectively. Most of the generated statistics are static diagrams or tables, but a few are interactive plots where the user can select for instance which sphere (ocean and sea ice, terrestrial, atmosphere) to visualise statistics for.

The home page of the ARCMAP web site provides a graphical user interface (GUI) where the location and some key characteristics of the in situ systems are presented on a dynamic map. Through the survey part of ARCMAP new observing systems and data collections can be easily registered. The survey consists of six parts whose content can be stored individually, to ease the task for the user. Responses to the questions of the survey are mapped to fields in the ARCMAP database. Fields containing single or multiple choice selections are used as the basis for the statistics generated by the system. The fields containing text provide information such as names of the observing systems and contact persons for them and their datasets, names for organisations coordinating the operation of the observing systems, as well as information elaborating the responses in the selection choice fields. Some text fields, such as names of the observing systems are used to label statistics plots and tables, while the majority is used in the assessment of observing capacities and gaps (Tjernstrøm et al., 2020).

The ARCMAP system is developed using Open-Source frameworks wq, Django REST and Leaflet (Hamre et al., 2020). It runs in a web browser, without the need for extra plugins. Version 1 was released mid November 2019 for the Polar Data Forum 3 conference. Since then, many features such as different plots and a polar stereographic map have been added to the home page of ARCMAP to present the location and some key characteristics of the assessed observing systems.

The ARCMAP survey application is built using two web frameworks: (1) the Django REST framework. and on top of that, (2) the WQ web questionnaire framework. Django REST is a general framework for building a website, and includes mechanisms for security, administration and composition of web pages. WQ is a framework for implementing XLSForms, which is a standard for creating and sharing forms in web pages. The WQ framework uses the Django REST framework as a base and provides a kick-start for building the survey application since it has some functionality for importing Excel files into the Django framework, tools for presenting the forms of the survey in web pages in the survey, and to help with updates of the web pages.

The Leaflet JavaScript library was used to implement the map presenting the location and selected characteristics on the ARCMAP home page. In this interactive map, an interactive overview map in polar stereographic projection has been developed. Each observing system is plotted, and a short information “bubble” is revealed when an observing system marker is clicked. The information for the observing systems is updated once per day from the ARCMAP survey database. A clustering method has been implemented to reduce the number of markers displayed at once at a given magnification. Clusters are shown as filled circles with a number within, denoting the number of observing systems the cluster includes. By clicking on a cluster, the map zooms in and the observing systems for that cluster are displayed, either as individual systems (shown as markers) or as smaller groups (clusters) of systems. Thus, clusters can include other clusters, which are opened as the user zooms into the map. Figures 1 and 2 show two examples of the geographic distribution of observing systems captured in the ARCMAP survey database.

Figure 1 Initial view of the overview map. Clusters of observation systems are shown as color-filled circles, when holding the mouse pointer over a circle, the area that the cluster covers is shown as a blue area. Single observation systems are shown as blue pin markers. When clicking on a blue pin marker, an information bubble is displayed.

Figure 2 Zooming in the overview map. When clicking on a cluster marker, the map will zoom in to display the observation systems covered by that cluster. Clusters can include other clusters in addition to single observation systems.

To facilitate a common environment for development and deployment, the complete ARCMAP survey application was first installed into a Docker container. A Docker container can be seen as a “miniserver” that is completely defined within a file (known as an image). This makes it possible to move an entire system between different computers and servers, guaranteeing software and data consistency across platforms.

A virtual server, arcmapp.nersc.no, was created with only a web server and the base Docker system installed. The Docker container for ARCMAP was moved to this server as a Docker image, which is represented as a single file that contains everything needed to run the Django WQ.IO system. The Docker image was imported and started by the Docker system on ARCMAP server. The web server is configured as a proxy to make it publicly available as shown in Figure 3. The ARCMAP database with all the data is stored outside the Docker container to facilitate easy backup and installation of new versions of the ARCMAP application.

Figure 3. Illustration of the ARCMAP architecture that shows the relationship between the main server, web server, Docker container with ARCMAP application and database to store the data. The user connects to <https://arcmmap.nersc.no/> with a web browser, the web server handles the user’s request and acts as a proxy to communicate directly with the ARCMAP system within the Docker container. The Docker container handles the connection to the ARCMAP database.

4.4 Information retrieved from ARCMAP

In this paper we use ARCMAP to obtain information about the observing systems that include ‘ocean sound’ as an observed variable. Out of 115 assessed observing systems eleven systems contained ‘ocean sound’. For the analysis we used the graphical and statistical functions of Microsoft Excel. In the following we provide some examples of information extracted for these observing systems, where we have limited our study to system characteristics of categorical type. We list the system characteristic title, its categories (response alternatives) and provide a brief interpretation when possible. For instance, the analysis revealed that many of the assessed acoustic systems appear to have poorly developed data storage capability. However, as the database is in a build-up phase, one should have in mind that any inference based on only 11 samples can only be tentative.

- **System category.** Multiple choice, 6 categories.

This system characteristic field provides information on the broader purpose of the observing system. From Fig. 4 we observe that the majority of systems (9) are purely focused, i.e., confined to specific themes or disciplines. Only one observing system is characterized as a broad network, including a broad range of interdisciplinary observations and projects, whereas one system is registered as both focused and broad. None of the remaining four categories were selected. There is a clear tendency for the acoustic observing systems to be focused, which is in general agreement with the general view that observing systems have a scientific motivation and are temporally and geographically limited.

Options:

Broad network (it includes a broad range of interdisciplinary observations and projects)

Focused network (is confined to specific themes or disciplines)

Commercial network (provides observational data for profit)

Operational network (feeding observations into weather service and forecast entities)

Resource-extraction network (conducts monitoring or baseline observations specifically for planned or ongoing resource extraction activities)

Distributed data (from many local networks)

Figure 4 Bar plot of the characteristic ‘System category’.

- **Scientific support.** Single choice, 5 choices.

Scientific support captures the extent and quality of human resources available to maintain the system, i.e. a key prerequisite for sustainability. From Fig. 5a we see that the typical response is 3 - "Technical expertise is available to support operation of the observing system" (5 responses). In general responses spread over all categories, and category 5 holding the best sustainability measure scores second highest (3 responses). This may lead to the conclusion that the situation is over all satisfactory with respect to available personnel resources.

- **Funding support.** Single choice. 5 choices

Funding support (Fig. 5b) seeks to measure the level of stability and sufficiency of available financial resources, again a key prerequisite for sustainability of operation. The typical response here is 2 - "Project based funding support available" (6 responses), with category 3 as number two - "as 2 + expectation of follow-on funding".

Figure 5. Bar plot of the characteristics (a) Scientific support and (b) Funding support.

- **Funding source.** Multiple choice, 4 categories

This system characteristic is related to the previous one in that also the international level of the funding body can be relevant for sustainability. Typically, sustainability is likely to be ensured the higher the international level. We see (Fig. 6) that the majority of systems receives national funding (8 solely, 2 in combination with international, EU and/or private funding); only one has EU as its main funding body.

Figure 6 Bar plot of the characteristics (a) Scientific support and (b) Funding support.

- **System standard.** Multiple choice, 5 categories.

Here the respondents were asked *Is any international/community standard implemented?* The typical response was ‘No’ (9 counts) as seen in Fig. 7a, i.e. no community standards are implemented, a characteristic generally associated with a low degree of sustainability.

- **Discovery service.** Multiple choice, 10 categories.

An important property of an observing system is that its data are findable (the ‘F’ in the FAIR-principles; Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016). Hence, the respondents were asked if their system supported any discovery service. Perhaps not surprising, the typical reply was ‘None’ (6 counts), with ‘I don’t know’ ranking as number two (3 counts; Fig. 7b). This negative result may also reflect that the survey was responded to by scientists, without any involvement of technical personnel that would probably be necessary for this question.

Figure 7 Pie charts of the characteristics (a) ‘System standard’ and (b) ‘Discovery service’. In (a) two unselected alternatives were “Yes, it applies to all collections, but it may vary from dataset to dataset” and “Other”. In (b) six unselected options were “OGC CSW”, “OGC GeoSPARQL”, “OpenSearch”, “OAI-PMH”, “CKAN”, “FTP”.

- **Data storage.** Multiple choice, 7 categories.

Again, to achieve sustainability, data needs to be stored in a reliable manner. All responses contain the option ‘Institutional’, most in combination with ‘Personal’ (n=5) and 4 in singularity (Fig. 8a). It is noteworthy that the definition of ‘Personal’ in this study explicitly excludes the ‘Institutional’ option, so it is reasonable to think that respondents have had in mind a personal duplication of the institutional data sets. Such apparent ambiguity in the category definitions blur the interpretation of responses and it will be natural to eliminate them as far as possible in future updates of the survey.

- **Data access.** Single choice, 9 categories.

Data access measures the ease with which data will be available for any user. From Fig. 8b we see again a clear tendency that ‘data is available on request to trusted users (Data validation is not yet completed, but data

may be available to beta-users for testing.)’ (n=7). I.e., data access is typically dependent of some personal interaction by the data originating person or institution.

Figure 8. Bar plot of the characteristics (a) ‘Data storage’ and (b) ‘Data access’.

● **Long term data preservation.** Single choice, 5 categories

This system characteristic picks up how the data is archived and the level of advancement of the archiving infrastructure. Although the typical response is ‘None’ (n=4), the responses are more evenly spread out on the first three categories (Fig. 9). A fairly high score (n=3) for category 3 indicates that at least part of the community reached a standard indicating that “each version archived at an institutional level on at least two media”.

Categories:

- 1, **A)** None (No archiving system in apparent use for the data collections)
- 2, **B)** Local archive retained by data collector which may be used to retrieve data on an ad hoc request basis, but is dependent upon the data collector or a single small group
- 3, **C)** Each version archived at an institutional level on at least two media (Data archival is transferred from the data collector to an institutionally maintained archive and formalized, stored on at least two media in two distinct locations)
- 4) Data, raw data and metadata are archived at a recognized data repository, national archive or international repository
- 5) As 4 + all versions of measurement series, metadata, software etc. retained, indexed and accessible upon request.

Figure 9 Bar plot of the characteristic ‘Long term data preservation’.

● **Combined properties**

A further step in the analysis could be to look at all characteristics in combination. For instance, clustering techniques or machine learning may be invoked to find out whether the data cluster around certain typical patterns in the multivariate space. As an example, with our small sample, we have plotted two characteristics against each other and observe the implied bivariate distribution. In this case we plot the fields Funding support and Scientific support against each other. In Fig. 10 we see that the mode (n=3) of the distribution is at (3, 3) which decodes to: “Technical expertise is available to support operation of the observing system (to ensure continuation of the measurements including maintenance and replacement of sensors, and secure data storage)” and “Project based funding support available (there is dedicated funding support, but it is tied to a project and therefore not continuous) + expectation of follow on founding (there is a reasonable expectation that funding will be renewed, for the same project or for other projects that may have slightly different focus but similar set of measurements) “. For this case the mode coincides with that of the single characteristic ‘Scientific support’, whereas for ‘Funding support’ it is one step above the mode of the characteristic viewed in isolation. From Fig. 10 it can be seen that for ‘Funding support’ = 2 (Project based funding) ‘Scientific support’ spread out almost over the entire scale. Once stepping up one unit in ‘Funding support’, the values become centered around (3,3). A possible interpretation may be that for low funding the scientific resource is funded elsewhere. Whereas, when some more funding is secured, hiring of technical personnel tends to be prioritized.

Figure 10 Scatter plot of the characteristics ‘Funding support’ vs ‘Scientific support’. The scores are provided to the right of the dot symbols. Unnumbered dots have score = 1.

4.5 Discussion

By taking all the results obtained in Section 4 together, we may obtain a general characteristic of the typical Arctic observing system observing ‘ocean sound’. One simple way to do this - based on the 11 surveyed ones – may be to add together the individual modes of each distribution. By doing so, we can state that the typical Arctic observing system has the following characteristics:

- Observing networks are focused on specific themes or disciplines
- Technical expertise is available to ensure continuation of the measurements including maintenance and replacement of sensors, and secure data storage
- Observation networks are project based and supported by national funding
- No standard for data encoding is implemented
- Data are stored partly in institutional or distributed systems
- No data discovery service is implemented
- No archiving system is in apparent use for the data collections.
- Data is available on request to trusted users.

The sample of examined systems (n=11) is too small to draw any wide conclusion, but as several of its statements appear to be congruent with general views as expressed in the introductory section, we may nevertheless claim that the analysis provides quantitative evidence backing up the general views held by the observing community. It will be interesting to see if the results will be robust when the analysis is repeated with a more populated database. Analysis of a larger sample could also explore whether application of clustering techniques will have any merit.

When it comes to the specific system characteristics, such as ‘Scientific support’, its relatively high score (n=3) obtained for the “best” category (=5) together with a high score (=5) for the mode, make it stand out among the other characteristics. This indicates that the sustainability aspect is over-all good regarding scientific support compared to the general state. Here we have assumed that the characteristic in consideration is at ordinal measure level, which is in general not the case. Some precautions should also be taken when interpreting the results. For instance, for characteristics such as ‘System standard’ and ‘Discovery service’ having high scores for categories as ‘No’, ‘None’ or ‘I do not know’ may indicate that the respondent did not understand the underlying questions. The typical respondent was a scientist, so in future revisions of the survey information that such questions be answered by technical experts should be added. Sporadic feedback to the designers also supports this view. Furthermore, for a characteristic like ‘Data storage’ the possibility of joint selection of two choices that by their definitions are mutually exclusive, should be avoided. Closer inspection of the scores of all the characteristics may provide further guidelines on revision of survey questions and response alternatives. Changing the alternatives for a question may invalidate previous responses. In such cases, the benefits of obtaining new information should be weighed against the effort needed to update already collected information.

The relatively low scores for the characteristics ‘Data storage’, ‘Data access’ and ‘Long term data preservation’ is also consistent with what was found in Section 2, that the investigated relevant data portals contained only a small fraction of passive acoustic data. The reason for this remains to be investigated. The apparent lack of fixed tags or keywords adds to this picture as free text searches using various sets of criteria seldom yield unique results. If database managers implement ‘ocean sound’ as a tag, it will be a step forward. Similarly, acousticians should report their data to the larger facilities.

4.6 Conclusion

ARCMAP has been designed as a user-friendly web system for collecting and maintaining information about Arctic in situ observing systems and data collections. It has also been demonstrated as an efficient tool to retrieve statistical information about Arctic acoustics observing systems with regard to their sustainability. A preliminary conclusion based on the small sample (n=11) of surveyed Arctic observing systems is that the typical system is focused, project based, funded nationally and has non-advanced routines for data storage and management, in agreement with the present general view. This result is based on the typical responses for each individual question independently.

Consistent with the statistical result, we also found that there are relatively few datasets on **passive** acoustic reported in the repositories such as PANGAEA or EMODNET. In addition, there are no unique search terms when searching for passive acoustic data. It is therefore recommended that databases holding acoustic data utilize the recently defined Essential Ocean Variable ‘ocean sound’ as a keyword, to ease searches and avoid ambiguities.

The meta-databases of IQOE and CAFF dedicated to acoustic observing systems can be valuable for further ingestion of data into ARCMAP, by identifying systems for assessment. It is also recommended that these and other relevant sites are considered for harvesting information to be utilized by ARCMAP and minimizing the effort for the responders.

4.7 Exploitation

ARCMAP can aid initiatives and organizations with a vested interest in the Arctic in their assessment of the current in situ observing capacity in the Arctic. The application enables detailed descriptions of in situ observing systems to be easily registered and updated. Traditional web survey tools are developed for general purposes such as customer surveys, opinion polls, event registration, and quizzes, where text input or selecting one or more options from a list of predefined alternatives suffice to capture the required information. In comparison, ARCMAP is designed to meet the needs of a specialized survey gathering geographic information such as locations of ocean moorings and land-based stations, through tailored input widgets (e.g., map components, multiple choice selections, latitude and longitude input fields).

Furthermore, ARCMAP supports automatic generation of statistical information and maps for analysis of different aspects of the registered systems. With survey responses stored in a database, new queries can be implemented with little effort to extract customized views of the accumulated information. Thus, ARCMAP can generate a set of statistical plots and tables to facilitate an overall assessment of the observing capacity of these systems combined. While ARCMAP was developed for use in the Arctic, the structure of the survey (i.e., the questions) and underlying database, are generic and can be set up for other regions. The application can be adapted to include other parameters or application domains, include new questions tailored for specific communities, or extend the assessment to data storage systems, to reach a wider user and stakeholder group. Moreover, ARCMAP can enhance its import capabilities from other in situ observing assets systems by making exchange agreements with the operators of these systems. This will increase the amount of information available in ARCMAP for use in assessment of the in situ observing capacity in the region it is set up for.

For the acoustics community in particular the inherent tagging in ARCMAP of the assessed observing systems with ‘ocean sound’ enables the user to extract or statistically analyse information on acoustic observing systems. This can in turn be used as a quantitative basis for, e.g., gap analyses or planning processes with regard to deployments of new acoustic equipment in the Arctic, negotiations versus funding agencies or other stakeholders, development of European or international research projects or programs, etc. The filtered information is differentiated with regard to various aspects of sustainability status, such as financial support, maintenance support, placement inside international organizations, data management and accessibility.

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5 A DATASET OF UNDERWATER PASSIVE ACOUSTIC RECORDINGS FROM A 2-YEAR MOORING DEPLOYMENT IN FRAM STRAIT (UNDER-ICE)

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Figure numbers are from Figure 1-10.

The UNDER-ICE acoustic thermometry experiment deployed 5 moorings in Fram Strait from 2014-2016. The mooring locations covered the central Fram Strait between 78° and 80° N and contained both mooring locations which were covered by sea ice most of the year and ice-free mooring locations. Each mooring consisted of a DSTAR control unit and of 10 hydrophones modules in an array configuration with a vertical distance of 9 m between hydrophones. Acoustic recordings from long deep-water moorings differ from bottom-mounted hydrophones as they can be influenced by noise from the mooring itself due to cable strumming in strong currents. An extensive quality control was therefore conducted with the data set. The fact that cable strumming correlates with strong currents and mooring pulldowns could be used to identify recordings that are potentially influenced by cable strumming. Quality flags denote which recordings are likely to be influenced by noise from cable strumming. Level 2 data from the experiment will be published as netcdf files containing noise level percentiles as a function of frequency. The netcdf files also contain all necessary metadata about the experiment and the processing.

5.1 Introduction

During the UNDER-ICE experiment 5 acoustic moorings (UI1 – UI5) were deployed in Fram Strait from September 2014 to July 2016 (Figure 1). The main purpose of the UNDER-ICE experiment was acoustic thermometry, for this purpose two of the moorings contained sound sources (UI2 and UI5, Storheim et al., 2021). All 5 moorings contained a distributed acoustic recording array consisting of 10 hydrophone modules (HMs) each controlled by a distributed simple tomographic acoustic receiver (D-STAR). The HMs recorded at programmed times every 3 hours to record the acoustic signal from the sound sources, each of these recordings is 130 s long. The programming of the recording times was such that the HMs did not record transmission from the sound source located on the same mooring as the hydrophone module. The recordings do contain the signal from sound sources that are not on the same mooring as the HM. However, the signal is so weak that it does not have any significant influence on the recorded noise level spectra, it is only identifiable by pulse compression. Because of a limit in the number of storable files on the instruments, the moorings stopped recording between January (UI1, UI3, UI4) and March 2016 (UI5). Mooring UI2 stopped recording in February 2016. In total there are 20 months of data with short acoustic recordings at regular intervals. The dataset presented here will be published in the Norwegian Marine Data Center (NMDC). It consists of processing level 2 data, which are percentile noise spectra for each recording. Processing level 1 data, which is sound spectra for each recording, might be published later. The dataset also contains mooring and processing metadata following the metadata standards of the NMDC. A quality flag value for each recording is included in the dataset, this denotes recordings which are influenced by mooring self-noise from cable strumming. The dataset is in netcdf format, with one netcdf file for each UNDER-ICE mooring.

Figure 1: The UNDER-ICE acoustic thermometry experiment in Fram Strait

Table 1: Mooring and hydrophone positions in UNDER-ICE experiment

Mooring	Position	Hydrophone module depths (m)*	Water depth (m)
UI1	8.752E, 77.909N	467, 476, 494, 503, 512, 521, 530, 539, 548	1413
UI2	3.191E, 78.015N	336, 327, 318, 309, 300, 291, 282, 273, 264, 255	3040
UI3	4.224W, 78.166N	317, 308, 299, 290, 281, 272, 263, 254, 245, 236	2209
UI4	4.727W, 80.003N	313, 304, 295, 286, 277, 268, 259, 250, 241, 232	1419
UI5	5.1239E, 79.856N	565, 556, 547, 538, 529, 520, 511, 502, 493	1372

* Hydrophones with retrieved data only, 2 hydrophone modules were lost due to flooding of the instrument. The hydrophone module depths are displayed in the order of the instrument numbers.

5.2 Data processing

The data processing for the UNDER-ICE passive acoustic data was more complex and extensive than what is usually done for passive acoustic data (Figure 2). There are two main reasons for that.

- First: the publication of the data should be done in a national data center, in this case the Norwegian Marine Data Center (NMDC). These data centers usually demand netcdf as the file format for the data. They also demand that the published files contain both experiment and processing metadata, which follow the metadata standards of the respective data center (Hamre et al., 2017). In the case of NMDC, this meant that the netcdf files of the dataset presented here contain 55 global attributes, all of which correspond to metadata

information. In addition, there are 16 attributes containing information about the instrument and metadata attributes for each stored variable.

- Second: The hydrophone modules in the UNDER-ICE experiment are located on long moorings, being situated at 1372 – 3040 m water depth (Table 1). Two of the moorings (UI2, UI5) include heavy sound sources. Due to the strong ocean currents in Fram Strait some of the moorings experienced strong pull-downs (up to 200 m). This can cause mooring self-noise from cable strumming, which influences the recording. Therefore, it was important to denote recordings where cable strumming was present or where it even might have caused data overload by a quality flag, so data users can exclude this part of the dataset if necessary.

Figure 2: Flow diagram for UNDER-ICE level 2 data processing, coloured outlines denote the main parts of the processing chain. Red: processing of acoustic data and calculation of percentile spectra. Yellow: setting thresholds for mooring motion, calculate quality flags. Green: collecting acoustic data, quality flags and metadata and save as netcdf file

The processing of the acoustic data was done as follows. The sample rate of the acoustic recordings is 1000 Hz. The measured raw signal in Volts was divided by the hydrophone sensitivity ($10^{-168/20}$ dB /1 μ Pa) and the amplitude gain ($10^{12/20}$) to calculate the measured pressure timeseries in μ Pa for each 130 s long recording. Acoustic spectrograms were calculated using a Hanning window with a length of 128 data points and a 50% overlap (Level 1 data). For each recording percentile spectra for the 10th, 50th and 90th percentile were calculated (Level 2 data, presented here). In addition, the 1st and 99th percentile spectra were calculated for quality control and testing purposes only, they are not part of the dataset for publication.

The quality evaluation of the passive acoustic data was done in two steps. In the first step, oversaturated recordings were identified and marked. The second step tried to identify instances of mooring self-noise from cable strumming by using vertical mooring motion data. Figure 3 shows how periods of high noise levels measured by an UNDER-ICE hydrophone module coincide with periods of mooring pushdown events by ocean currents. This correspondence was used to find threshold values of vertical mooring displacement below which the influence of cable strumming on the acoustic recording is negligible. Different thresholds were tested and compared to determine the motion threshold for each hydrophone module. Figure 4 shows an example of such a comparison. For each hydrophone module the percentile spectra for the 1st, 10th, 50th, 90th and 99th percentile were plotted for different threshold values of vertical mooring displacement (Figure 4). Strumming noise was identifiable by spectral lines and by increased noise levels at the lowest frequencies. The threshold was chosen such that no spectral lines were present at the 90th percentile. In addition, the noise levels using the chosen threshold had to be similar to the noise levels that would have resulted from choosing a smaller threshold.

Figure 3: Vertical mooring displacement (red line) and 50th percentile spectrogram of the recorded underwater noise (colormap) for hydrophone module 542, which is situated on mooring UI5.

Figure 4: Example of the type of plot used to identify vertical mooring displacement thresholds. Only data points corresponding to vertical mooring displacements $mothinZ$ less than the threshold value are included in the percentile spectra with different threshold values applied for each panel. The panels show the resulting percentile spectra after excluding data points corresponding to vertical mooring displacements larger than the threshold. The number of remaining data points after the exclusion is denoted for each panel. Upper panel: vertical mooring displacement threshold 1 m, 100 data points remaining. Middle panel: vertical mooring displacement threshold 2 m, 972 data points remaining. Lower panel: vertical mooring displacement threshold 3 m, 2796 data points remaining.

Figure 5: Percentile spectra of two recordings from the same hydrophone module (HM 543, mooring UI5). The recording on the left panel was assigned quality flag 4 (bad data / cable strumming). The recording on the right panel was assigned quality flag 2 (probably good data). The effects of the cable strumming are visible at all plotted percentiles and include both spectral lines and a general increase of the measured noise levels.

Figure 5 shows the examples of the resulting percentile spectra, which will be published in the Norwegian Marine Data Center (NMDC) as the level 2 passive acoustic data from the UNDER-ICE experiment. For each recording, there is one set of three percentile spectra for the 10th, 50th and 90th percentile spectrum. The dataset also contains a quality flag for each of the recordings, denoting if the recording was influenced by mooring self-noise from cable strumming. The definitions of the quality flag values follow standards from NMDC (Hamre et al. 2017). Quality flag 2 denotes “probably good data”, while quality flag 4 denotes “bad data, cable strumming”.

The amount of data which is flagged as influenced by cable strumming (quality flag 4, bad data) differs strongly between moorings, depending on the strength of the ocean currents at the different mooring locations. Figures 6-10 present an overview of the results from moorings UI1-UI5. The amount of data flagged with quality flag 4 differs strongly between moorings. While hardly any data from mooring UI4 is labelled with quality flag 4, about 90% of the recordings from mooring UI5 are influenced by cable strumming and therefore assigned quality flag 4. The bad data is most prevalent during winter and early spring. It is worth noting, however, that good recordings can still be found at practically any time of the year, whenever there is a period of weak ocean currents. The data quality of the recordings from moorings UI1 and UI3 is similar to those from mooring UI5. At mooring UI2 the vertical mooring positioning proved to be unreliable resulting in spikes and periods of wrong mooring depth estimates. Therefore, no mooring motion thresholds could be defined for UI2 and all recordings from UI2 had to be flagged with quality flag 4. At mooring UI3, the recordings of the two uppermost hydrophone modules had to be flagged with quality flag 4, because the data was found to be influenced by cable strumming irrespective of the mooring motion threshold chosen.

Figure 6: Overview of data from mooring UII, the uppermost hydrophone module 501 and the lowermost hydrophone module 510 are plotted. Noise levels are 50th percentile spectra of each recording (panel 1+3). Blue bars (quality flag 4) denote bad data which is influenced by cable strumming, areas without blue bars (quality flag 2) denote probably good data (panel 2+4).

Figure 7: Overview of data from mooring UI2, the lowermost hydrophone module 511 and the uppermost hydrophone module 520 are plotted. Noise levels are 50th percentile spectra of each recording (panel 1+3).. Blue bars (quality flag 4) denote bad data which is influenced by cable strumming; at mooring UI2 all recorded acoustic data had to be flagged with quality flag 4, because the mooring motion data were erroneous.

Figure 8: Overview of data from mooring UI3, the lowermost hydrophone module 521 and the uppermost hydrophone module 530 are plotted. Noise levels are 50th percentile spectra of each recording (panel 1+3). Blue bars (quality flag 4) denote bad data which is influenced by cable strumming, areas without blue bars (quality flag 2) denote probably good data (panel 2+4). All data from hydrophones 529 and 530 at mooring UI3 was assigned quality flag 4.

Figure 9: Overview of data from mooring UI4, the lowermost hydrophone module 531 and the uppermost hydrophone module 540 are plotted. Noise levels are 50th percentile spectra of each recording (panel 1+3). Blue bars (quality flag 4) denote bad data which is influenced by cable strumming, areas without blue bars (quality flag 2) denote probably good data (panel 2+4).

Figure 10: Overview of data from mooring UI5, the lowermost hydrophone module 541 and the uppermost hydrophone module 550 are plotted. Noise levels are 50th percentile spectra of each recording (panel 1+3). Blue bars (quality flag 4) denote bad data which is influenced by cable strumming, areas without blue bars (quality flag 2) denote probably good data (panel 2+4).

5.3 Conclusion

A processing chain for level 2 passive acoustic data from a distributed acoustic array containing autonomous hydrophone modules was established. The dataset presented here contains level 2 data from 20 months of passive acoustic recordings from 5 moorings deployed by the UNDER-ICE project in Fram Strait. The level 2 acoustic data consists of 10th, 50th, and 90th percentile spectra for each of the 130s long passive acoustic recordings. The dataset includes quality flags for each recording and all mooring and processing metadata. The data is ready for publication in netcdf format at the Norwegian Marine Data Center (NMDC).

The processing routines presented here will be usable for ongoing future experiments using autonomous hydrophone modules (e.g. the Coordinated Arctic Acoustic Thermometry Experiment, CAATEX). The scripts

are written in such a way that the processing can be scaled up for any number of hydrophone modules connected to D-STAR (Distributed Simple Tomographic Acoustic Receiver) control units.

The quality flags included in the netcdf files together with the data are of great importance as acoustic recordings from moorings can be strongly influenced by noise from cable strumming if the mooring experiences strong ocean currents. Cable strumming can change the 50th percentile noise spectra by more than 20 dB. The inclusion of quality flags together with the data will facilitate the usage of the data by other researchers. In our opinion this justifies that amount of work necessary to produce the quality flags. The mooring and processing metadata included in the netcdf files will hopefully increase the usability of the data and ensure that the data is searchable on major data portals.

5.4 Exploitation, data quality and outlook

A main use for the data sets presented here will be to estimate year-round background levels of underwater noise in the Fram Strait area. The quality flags should be used as a filter for this purpose. Biological use will probably be limited to species which produce low-frequency sound, such as for example Finn whales, as the upper frequency limit of 1000 Hz will be too low for the identification and study of many marine mammal species.

It remains to be seen, which additional benefits can be gained from having 10 hydrophones on each mooring. There might be some potential for studying the depth dependence of the underwater noise. However, the mooring configuration put the hydrophones quite close to each other, so they only cover a small part of the water column. One application might be the error estimation of the underwater noise measurement, that is to gain better insight on the representativeness of single hydrophone recordings, i.e. what part of a recording is representative of the wider environment and what are local effects close to the hydrophone. The duplication of the hydrophones could also be used to further filter the data to the most quiet recording at each point in time.

Two main factors seem to influence the quality of the recorded acoustic data. First, the strength of the currents at the mooring location, and secondly, the mooring equipment, which influenced the amount of mooring pull-down by current. Moorings which contained the large sound sources experienced stronger pull-downs than moorings which only contained smaller acoustic receivers.

One conclusion of this work is that the usability of acoustic recordings from long moorings depends strongly on the mooring location and the ocean environment of the mooring. From a purely passive acoustics point of view moorings for acoustic recordings should be preferably placed at sites with weak ocean currents. Therefore, if several sites are possible for the other scientific purposes of the mooring, the site with the smaller currents could be chosen to increase the usability of the mooring for acoustic recordings. And in cases where there is a whole array of moorings planned, it might be best to concentrate most of the passive acoustic equipment on those moorings which are expected to encounter the weakest currents.

5.5 References

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6 ANALYSIS OF SIGNAL PROPAGATION IN THE UNDER-ICE EXPERIMENT

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Fram Strait is the main gateway between the Arctic- and the Atlantic Ocean and is a region with complex oceanographic conditions. From 2014 to 2016, five acoustic moorings were deployed across the strait as a part of the UNDER-ICE project (funded by the Research Council of Norway). The main objective was to measure the heat-exchange through the Strait, based on average temperature measurements made using acoustic tomography. Transmissions were made every third hour along 7 different transects.

The initial analysis of the results from the northernmost transect, a 180 km long transect from East to West at 80 N across the strait, showed that the 90 s long signal vanished during some time periods.

Results from one of the sections across the Strait are presented, along with an analysis of the mooring motion, as well as the collected oceanographic data. The analysis indicates that the loss of the signal is caused by a combination of the pull-down of the acoustic source due to the currents, as well as the oceanographic conditions.

6.1 INTRODUCTION

The Fram Strait between Greenland and Svalbard is the only deep water connection between the interior Arctic Ocean (AO) and the rest of the oceans.⁵ Hot water is transported into the interior Arctic by the East- Greenland Current (EGC), and cold fresh water comes out via the West-Spitzbergen Current (WSC). The narrow strait and shallow depths leads to a mixing of EGC and WSC, resulting in complex oceanographic and acoustical conditions. Monitoring of the heat flux going through the strait is important as it could provide information about the heating of the AO.

From 2008-2009, two moorings were deployed during the DAMOCLES project.⁸ The results indicated that acoustic tomography could be used to measure average temperature. However, the complex oceanographic conditions lead to more challenging acoustic propagation, compared to e.g. the lower latitudes. In 2010, four moorings were deployed as a part of the ACOBAR project. UNDER-ICE, which is discussed in the present paper, is the third acoustic tomography experiment lead by NERSC in the Fram Strait. The experience from the previous experiments, combined with new instruments, was used in 2014-2016 when five moorings were deployed.

The focus of this paper is to present the acoustic data from the receptions of the signals from one of the acoustic sources, together with some of the oceanographic data, and discuss potential reasons for the lack of receptions. Acoustic and oceanographic measurements are presented and discussed. An ice-ocean model is used in the analysis of the results to get a better understanding of the effects observed in the data. An accompanying paper¹ addresses the acoustic propagation between the moorings, based on modelling.

6.2 EXPERIMENT CONFIGURATION AND INSTRUMENTATION

In September of 2014, five moorings were deployed from the Norwegian coast guard vessel KV Svalbard in the Fram Strait. Figure 1 shows the mooring configuration and acoustic paths, in addition to the bathymetry obtained from the International Bathymetric Charts of the Arctic Ocean (IBCAO).² The acoustic sources were located on the UI2 and UI5 moorings, i.e. in the center of the Strait and in the WSC, respectively. Each mooring was equipped with 10 self-contained hydrophone modules (HM), spaced 9 m apart. Data is stored on memory cards inside the HM's, and they are powered by a Lithium battery cell. The HM's are also equipped with a high-precision thermistor (± 0.005 °C),⁶ making temperature measurements every 20 minutes.

The HM's are controlled via an inductive link by a D-STAR controller. The D-STAR also keep track of the time, and controls the transmissions from the sources. The source at UI2 transmitted every 3rd hour on every odd yeardays, and the source at UI5 transmitted every 3rd hour each day.

The source is a Webb sweeper source of organ-pipe design, which does not change frequency with depth. The acoustic sources transmitted linear sweeps from 200 Hz to 300 Hz with a 90 s long duration. Matched-filtering of the data is performed to compress the signal into a 10 ms long pulse, suitable for detection. Afterwards, the processed data from each hydrophone was beamformed to provide information about the arrival angle at the receiver array. The travel-time, arrival angle, and intensity of each reception was recorded. The travel-times

have been corrected for clock drift in the D-STAR controller, and mooring motion on both the source and receiver moorings.

The northernmost moorings, UI4 and UI5, were augmented with oceanographic instruments. UI4 was equipped with 6 Sea-Bird SBE37 (temperature, salinity and pressure) and SBE39 (temperature) sensors, and one Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP). UI5 had 6 SBE-37/39 sensors and two ADCP's.

Each mooring had a transponder network deployed around it, referred to as a *Long Baseline Acoustic Navigation Network*.⁶ Interrogation pings are transmitted from the D-STAR's, and the unique replies are recorded by both the D-STAR and the HM's. This was used to triangulate the position of each hydrophone module, as well as the D-STAR controller in 3 dimensions (the horizontal xy plane, and depth z), 10 minutes before and after each transmission.

Figure 1: Configuration of the UNDER-ICE tomographic experiment in the Fram Strait. The dots indicate the mooring locations, and the interconnecting lines indicate the different acoustic paths. The contour plot is the bathymetry obtained from IBCAO.

Several oceanographic measurements were made during the deployment and recovery cruises, such as Expendable Bathythermographs (XBT), in addition to the *in-situ* measurements on the moorings. These measurements are valuable for the acoustics, e.g. to map potential sound channels, and are used in the survey of the anchor and transponder locations.

6.3 THE GECCO OCEAN MODEL

The German partner of the ECCO effort (GECCO), has released a 10 year long dataset^{4,7} with daily fields from 2007 to 2016. It's a reanalysis with observations assimilated into it, such as the 2018 World Ocean Atlas. The nominal resolution is 16 km in the horizontal plane, but with higher resolution in certain areas, and there are 50 depth levels. The model contains sea-ice concentration and thickness, zonal and meridional ocean current components (u and v , respectively), temperature, and salinity, amongst others.

6.4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

6.4.1 ACOUSTIC ARRIVALS

Figure 2 shows a dot-plot of the arrivals (matched filtered and beamformed) at the four receiver moorings, for the transmissions from UI5. These dots indicates the travel time (y -axis), arrival angle (color), and intensity (diameter) of the different arrivals during the experiment (x -axis).

Receptions from the source are observed at all moorings, except UI3, from the start of the experiment. The arrivals appear to stop in the end of November 2014, and return in May of 2015. Later arrivals (with respect to travel time) are seen at both UI1 and UI4, indicating that sound propagating deeper in the ocean reached the receiver.

Figure 2: Dotplot of the arrivals recorded at UI1 (a), UI2 (b), UI3 (c), and UI4 (d), from transmissions from the acoustic source at UI5, during the experiment period.

A similar break in transmissions is seen on all the moorings until December of 2015. An increase in the number of arrivals is prominent in this period compared the earlier parts, especially at UI2 and UI4. The end of receptions in the beginning of 2016 was due to the maximum file capacity of the HM's was reached. The spurious arrivals are assumed to be false detections.

The reason for the lack of receptions is not known. Based on the observations made in Figure 2, the most likely cause for the dropout in signals, is the sound source itself. It is plausible that the source, for some reason (e.g. electrical, mechanical or software), did not transmit during these periods. This is based on the fact that the four receiver moorings are located at four completely different locations in the Strait. However, diagnostic information about the performance of the source was not available. Thus it is impossible to tell if the sound source actually transmitted or not, and if so, at what level.

6.4.2 MOORING MOTION

The mooring motion, i.e. how the mooring is influenced by and moves with the ocean currents, is also a potential source for the lack of receptions. Figure 3 shows the vertical motion of the acoustic source at UI5, i.e. the actual source depth, as a function of time. This is obtained from the transponder network surrounding the moorings, computed every 3rd hour. The nominal and intended source depth were 600 m. However, the strong currents in the WSC combined with the drag of the mooring, lead to significant pulldowns of the mooring. This is particularly seen during the winter months from January 2014 to May of 2015. A similar behavior is also observed from December 2015 to the end of the recordings. The currents also induce horizontal movement, but this does not influence the acoustic propagation as the movement is in the same water layer.

Figure 3: Vertical mooring motion of the acoustic source (a), and a corresponding histogram (b).

The changes in depth shown in Figure 3 (a) are somewhat exaggerated due to the plotting. Statistical measures provide a better overview of the data. A summary of some statistical parameters of the vertical motion is given in Table 1. The maximum depth of the source was 784 m, i.e. a pulldown of 184 m from the nominal depth. Such pulldowns could result in the sound signals to be transmitted into different water layers than intended, and thus potentially trapping the sound. The percentiles indicate that the source was above 610 m for 75 % of the time, indicating that the pulldowns are relatively short in duration.

Table 1: Statistics of the vertical motion of the acoustic source at the UI5 mooring.

Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Median	Percentiles			
				10 %	25 %	75 %	90 %
597.0 m	783.9 m	609.8 m	602.5 m	599.4 m	600.3 m	610.2 m	627.9 m

6.4.3 SEA-ICE

The Fram Strait is also partially covered by sea-ice, as ice is transported out along the Eastern side of Greenland. Due to the oceanography, most of the sound interacts with the top surface while propagating towards the receiver. When sea-ice is present, scattering in all directions occur, which in turn leads to a loss in signal strength. An example of the sea-ice cover is shown in Figure 8 (b). This is also a representative illustration of the sea-ice conditions in Fram Strait. The ice-edge typically lies along the line from UI5 to UI3, with UI4 covered by ice most of the time, and UI1 and UI2 in open water.

While sea-ice certainly can have a significant influence on acoustic propagation, this cannot be the singular reason for the effects observed here, as several of the receivers were in open water during the loss of signal.

6.4.4 OCEANOGRAPHIC CONDITIONS

Figure 4 shows the temperature and derived sound speed profile from an XBT cast taken at UI5 during deployment. A surface duct down to approximately 100 m, another duct between 100 m and 600 m, and what can potentially be a third duct from 600 m down to 1000 m. The nominal depth of the acoustic source is 600

m, i.e. in the transition between two ducts. With the pulldowns shown in Figure 3, transmissions would occur in the lower duct. The acoustic propagation under different conditions is studied in more detail in.¹

Figure 4: XBT cast taken at the UI5 location on 2014-09-11. Both temperature (blue) and derived sound speed (orange) is shown. The latter is computed using a constant salinity profile of 30 ppt.

Figure 5 shows the temperature profiles obtained from a series of XBT casts along the UI3 to UI5 transect, taken in July of 2016. There is an approximately 200 m thick layer of warm water, then a 400 m layer of cooler water. The temperature goes sub-zero and starts to stabilize after 1000 m. This specific transect was taken partly along the ice edge, and the UI3 mooring was inside the ice. This is seen in the cold layers near the surface, particularly at the first 20 km from UI3.

Figure 5: Temperature profiles obtained from XBT's taken along the UI3 to UI5 transect in 2014. The black line shows the bathymetric profile along the track, obtained from IBCAO.

6.5 RESULTS FROM THE GECCO MODEL

The data from the ice-ocean model can be used to get a better understanding of the overall processes that are going on, as well as the for the acoustic propagation. An example is shown here for the acoustic propagation between UI5 and UI4, computed for a static source depth of 600 m and receiver depth of 250 m. The surface

is flat, and the bottom topography is obtained from IBCAO. As shown in Section 4, this is a simplification compared to the acoustic experiment since 1) the source depth is constant, and 2) a point receiver is used. However, it illustrates the use of modelling combined with ocean model data. A more detailed analysis and discussion is given in ¹.

The daily fields provided by the GECCO model is also a valuable resource in terms of analyzing the acoustic propagation between the different moorings. A number of acoustic models, e.g., BELLHOP and RAM, are readily available and well established. These models use sound speed profiles or fields as input, which can be computed from the temperature, salinity and depth given in the GECCO dataset. Additionally, BELLHOP can also include scattering from a rough surface (e.g., sea-ice, where the sea-ice thickness is also available in the dataset), but this is not included in the present work.

Figure 6 shows the average temperature along the UI5-UI4 transect, obtained from the GECCO model. The plot shows the transect with longitude on the x -axis, where UI4 is located on the left-hand side, and UI5 on the right. The warm part on the eastern side is the West-Spitzbergen current and extends down to 1000 m depth. On the western side, a cold upper layer is seen. This is the East-Greenland current which is typically covered by sea-ice. This cold layer is what protects the sea-ice from the warmer deeper layers and prevents melting.

Figure 6: Average temperature calculated for GECCO data from 2014-09-01 to 2016-07-31 along the UI5-UI4 transect. The gray part illustrates the bathymetry obtained from IBCAO.

Each daily temperature- and salinity field is extracted for the period of interest and used as input to calculate the sound speed field. This is in turn used as input to BELLHOP where eigenrays are modelled for a series of launch angles from the source at 600 m depth. An example of eigenray paths is shown in Figure 7, as a function of depth and range from UI5. The single receiver is at 250 m.

Figure 7: Eigenray-paths connecting the source at 600 m and receiver at 250 for the UI5-UI4 transect, calculated with BELLHOP and a daily field sound speed field from 2019-09-01 calculated from model data obtained from the GECCO dataset. The gray part illustrates the bathymetry obtained from IBCAO.

Figure 8 shows the range-average temperature vs time along the UI5-UI4 transect, and a dot-plot of the arrivals simulated with BELLHOP for daily sound-speed fields obtained from the GECCO dataset. The dot-plot is created by extracting the travel-times and arrival angles from the eigenrays illustrated in Figure 6 and is similar to the plot for the measurements (c.f. Figure 2). In (a) the temperature is seen to be very stable below 1500 m. In the upper part of the water column, warming is observed, particularly for the upper 500 m. This is the effect of the WSC.

(a)

(b)

Figure 8: Range-average temperature (a) along the UI5-UI4 transect, calculated for the GECCO data from 2014-09-01 to 2016-07-31, shown as a function of time and depth. In (b), a dot-plot of the arrivals for a source at 600 m at UI5 and a receiver at 250 m at UI4, calculated with daily fields from GECCO, is shown.

For the acoustic arrivals, shown in (b), a clear correlation between the warming and the travel time is seen. The deeper propagating arrivals, shown here in green and purple, normally arrives first. This is due to the higher sound speed deeper down, which compensates for the increased path lengths. These arrivals remain stable throughout the period, with typical variations less than 100 ms. The arrivals that have propagated in shallow water (blue), are much more sensitive to the changes in sound speed / temperature. The higher temperatures result in a lower travel time which equals that of the deeper arrivals, such as in November-December of both 2014 and 2015. When the temperature cools down in the upper layer the travel time increases, which in turn leads to a separation in time with respect to the deeper arrivals. Changes of up to 1 s can be seen, such as between December 2014 and February of 2015. This separation is more advantageous compared to one big cluster of arrivals, e.g., for acoustic tomography.

Figure 9 shows the temperature measurements from the HM's on UI5 and UI4 during the experiment, along with the depth variation of the instruments. The temperature measurements were taken every 20 minutes. The pull-downs on UI4 was less than 3 m. At UI5 (a), ploods of warm water are present above 300 m from October through December of 2014, as well as in 2015. The temperature at UI4 remains more stable than at UI5, but there are also periods with warmer water. Similar results are also seen in the model data presented in Figure 8.

(a)

(b)

Figure 9: *In-situ* temperature measurements from the hydrophones and oceanographic instruments on UI5 (a) and UI4 (b), also as a function of depth.

The mooring motion, and thus the currents, is also an interesting parameter. Figure 10 shows the source mooring motion and data of current speed and direction measurements made by an upward-looking ADCP on the UI5 source mooring at 250 m depth. There’s good correspondence between the current speed (b) and the pulldowns observed in the mooring motion (a). The vertical profiles of the speed also indicates that the entire water masses above the ADCP is moving, not just specific layers. This is also observed in the model data, c.f. Figure 10 (b).

Figure 10: Time-series of the vertical motion of the sound source (a) derived from the transponder network, magnitude of the currents obtained from the GECCO model (b), and current speed (c) and direction (d) as measured by the upward-looking ADCP on UI5.

The significant pulldowns of the moorings can be studied more in detail using an ocean model to get a better overview of the big picture, rather than just the *in-situ* measurements performed by ADCP's at the mooring locations. Figure 11 shows the magnitude of the zonal and meridional ocean currents from the GECCO model on 23rd of March 2015, at 139 m depth. This corresponds to one of the days with significant pulldowns, and the depth is close to that of the nominal depth of the top sphere on the mooring. UI1 and UI5, located in the WSC, are subject to significant current speeds. This is in agreement with the model data.

Figure 11: Magnitude of the zonal and meridional current components at 139 m depth (a), and sea-ice concentration (b) on 2015-03-23, obtained from the GECCO model. The mean and standard deviation of the sea-ice concentration for the period 2014-09-01 to 2016-07-31 is shown in (c) and (d), respectively. The red markers indicate the UNDER-ICE mooring locations.

While the daily fields can be studied in detail to investigate certain effects, statistical metrics provides a simple overview of the time-varying data, which in this case spans almost two years. Figure 12 shows the mean values and the corresponding standard deviations of the current magnitude at 139 m and 553 m depth, from 2014-09-01 to 2016-07-31. UI1 and UI5 are located in the WSC, which is quite strong. UI3 and UI4 appears to be just east of the EGC. The currents are less strong at 553 m (b) compared to 139 m (a). Additionally, the variability is higher at 139 m compared to at 553 m, as seen in the plots of the standard deviations (c) and (d). This indicates that the top sphere may be the cause for the significant mooring motion on UI5, perhaps because of too little buoyancy or too much drag. However, the drag of the entire mooring must be taken into account in such an analysis, as there might be strong currents deeper down.

Figure 12: Mean (upper row) and standard deviation (middle row) of the magnitude of the zonal and meridional current components at 139 m depth (a and c), and 553 m (b and d), from 2014-09-01 to 2016-07-31, obtained from the GECCO model. The red markers indicate the UNDER-ICE mooring locations.

6.6 SUMMARY

Results from the acoustic and oceanographic instruments deployed during the UNDER-ICE experiment in Fram Strait have been presented. The receptions of the source signal transmitted from UI5 has been discussed, along with several potential reasons for the lack of receptions during some time periods. No specific cause has yet been identified. Minor changes in the experiment setup, such as recording the source signals on the mooring that is transmitting, would tell if the source was transmitting, and at what power, which would narrow down the list of reasons. This feature does however come at a cost, namely increased battery consumption and storage requirement.

An ice-ocean model has been used in the analysis of the acoustic propagation and oceanographic conditions during the experiment period. Temperature and ocean currents have qualitatively been compared with observations, and temperature and salinity has been used to compute the input sound speed fields to an acoustic model. Some examples are shown here, but the possibilities with such a model dataset are much higher. The use of ice-ocean models, combined with acoustic modelling, can be a powerful and useful combination, both in terms of planning and analysis of results from experiments. The model used here is a reanalysis, i.e. with *in-situ* observations of the ocean assimilated into the model, and the results are only available after the fact.

While this is most useful to aid in the analysis of experimental data, the model data still provides historical information that can be used in e.g., planning of experiments, and particularly acoustic tomography experiments since the acoustic propagation is so important.

6.7 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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7 USING ICE-OCEAN ENVIRONMENT FROM REANALYSIS INTO BELLHOP TO BETTER UNDERSTAND SOUND PROPAGATION IN THE FRAM STRAIT

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As a part of the UNDER-ICE experiment, acoustic signals were sent from a fixed position (600m under the water surface) west of Svalbard across the Fram Strait to a vertical receiver array on a mooring 200 km away. The UNDER-ICE experiment was set up to transmit for two years. The ice conditions along the section varied between partially to fully ice-covered fields according to the ice conditions throughout the 2-year experiment. However, after the experiment, it was found that the signals from the sources were only received in shorter periods during the experiment. In this paper, we investigate several physical characteristics that may be related to the lack of received signals, such as the environmental conditions (e.g., sea ice or oceanographic fronts) and the changes in the source depths during the experiment. In this work, we use the ice-ocean fields from a model reanalysis covering the experimental period. The reanalysis field is compared to oceanographic data obtained during the initial phase of the experiment. The Bellhop model is used to simulate the transmission of acoustic signals using ice-ocean fields from the reanalysis.

7.1 Introduction

With the decline of the Arctic Sea ice in recent decades, the sea ice field is transitioning to a more dynamic state containing younger and thinner ice. This influences the acoustic propagation and the natural sources of sound in the central Arctic (e.g., Worcester et al. 2021). In many ways, a steadily increasing part of the central Arctic transfers to become more similar to dynamics and gradients previously only observed in the marginal ice zone (MIZ). Therefore, the MIZ can be seen as a place to study the dynamics and the acoustic environment that will become more normal in the central Arctic.

The geographical area in this work is the MIZ in the Fram Strait. The Fram strait, between Svalbard and Greenland, is the main gateway for water exchange between the Atlantic Ocean and the eastern part of the Arctic Ocean. The strait is a climatic chokepoint for the Arctic Ocean and essential for the ocean heat budget in the Arctic Ocean. Warm water flows northward along the coast of Spitsbergen, turns east North of Svalbard, and brings Atlantic water into the Arctic Basin. In the western part of the Fram Strait, cold and “fresh” water is brought out of the Arctic Basin along the coast of Greenland into the Nordic Seas and the Atlantic Ocean. Therefore, the east of the Fram strait is open water while the west of Fram strait is commonly dominated by more or less dense fields of drifting sea ice. The location of the MIZ varies with seasons and is therefore also referred to as the seasonal ice zone.

Due to the very complex and dynamic oceanography, many short-term and long-term acoustic experiments were carried out in the 1980s and 1990s. The experiments were designed to investigate the ice-ocean processes, ambient noise (e.g., Johannessen et al., 2003), and acoustic propagation (e.g., Dyer et al., 1987, Dahl et al., 1998), including a year-long Greenland Sea tomography experiment 1988-1989. These previous studies showed that the acoustic characteristics are affected by the strong horizontal and vertical variability in the MIZ and the strong temporal variability. After the end of the cold war, there was a long break in acoustic experiments in the Arctic. From 2008 to 2016, a number of tomographic experiments and communication experiments were carried out in the Fram Strait (e.g., Sagen et al. 2017, Hope et al., 2017).

The reflection and scattering due to the rough elastic surfaces are considered as the main difficulty in modeling sound propagation in ice-covered regions. Therefore, the inclusion of reflection and scattering have been a central topic in many polar acoustic studies. Alexander et al. (2013) used the Bellhop model (Porter, 2011) to investigate the propagation losses of 10kHz acoustic signal generated at 20 m depth over a distance of 20 km. Hope et al. (2017) simulated the acoustic propagation at 900 Hz in the Fram Strait using the OASES model. The simulations were compared to observed receptions of signals sent from the icebreaker KV Svalbard as it was moving away from the receiver unit. Their study showed that the acoustic propagation at 900 Hz primarily depends on the sea ice roughness rather than other elastic parameters. Collins et al. (2019) used the parabolic equation method and experimental acoustic data from the Canada Basin Acoustic Propagation Experiment to investigate the capability to model the acoustic propagation in a large-scale ocean environment with gradual

horizontal variations in ice-ocean parameters. As a result of their work, they developed an improved method for including range-dependent ice thickness into the parabolic equation for simulations at frequencies below a couple of hundred Hz. Ivakin et al. (2020) used the elastic parabolic equation method for echo sounders at much higher frequencies to quantitatively analyze and explain the time dependence of low- and mid-frequency transmission loss to develop a wide-area synoptic assessment of ice type distribution.

In this paper, we will address the UNDER-ICE acoustic tomography experiment that took place in 2014-2016 in the central part of the Fram Strait (Fig.1) (Storheim et al. (2018, 2020)). In this experiment, a tomographic network of five acoustic moorings was deployed; two of them carried acoustic sweeper sources (200-300 Hz). All five moorings had 100 m long receiver arrays with 10 synchronized self-contained hydrophone modules (see Storheim et al., 2021). After recovery, it was found that one of the sources stopped working after 5 months due to technical failure. Signals from the other source were received in shorter and longer periods until the recordings stopped in February 2016. Based on this situation, we have investigated if the environmental conditions or mooring motion could prevent the acoustic signal from being detected at the receiver array 192 km away from the source. Selected physical parameters that could be related to the failure of receiving signals have been investigated, e.g., sea ice, oceanographic fronts or mooring motion. To carry out the study, we use an ice-ocean reanalysis prepared for the INTAROS project (Lyu et al., 2021) as input to the Bellhop model (Porter, 2011).

7.2 Observations and models

7.2.1 OBSERVING the FRAM STRAIT

Extensive work has been done on observing and modeling cold and warm water transports through the Fram Strait, but the work is challenging because of the complex circulation in the strait. The warmer and northbound West Spitsbergen current interacts with the southbound fresher and colder East Greenland Current. A monitoring system consisting of 14-17 oceanographic moorings has been operated since 1996 (Appen et al., 2016), but the moorings could not resolve and account for the mesoscale features or the significant recirculation in the estimation of the transports through the strait.

Furthermore, ocean modeling systems also struggle to provide realistic simulations of the very complex circulation pattern in the strait. This was the rationale for setting up tomographic systems and to combine the mean averaged measurements of sound speed/ocean temperature with ice-ocean modeling systems through assimilation (Sagen et al., 2017 and Geyer et al., 2019), which started in the DAMOCLES and ACOBAR projects and continued in the UNDER-ICE project. Figure 1 shows the location of the experiments from these three projects.

Figure 1. Map of moorings configuration during the UNDER-ICE (2014-2016), ACOBAR (2010-2012), and DAMOCLES 2008-2009).

7.2.2 The UNDER-ICE experiment

The details of the UNDER-ICE field experiment are described in Storheim et al. (2018, 2021). The two acoustic sources (UI-2 and UI-5) were programmed to transmit signals every 8 hours for two years. The signals were received at four 100 m long vertical receiver moorings, each equipped with 10 hydrophones. The

experiment was designed to give signal propagation along 8 tracks, indicated by the red lines in Fig.1. After the experiment was completed and the data analysis was progressing, it was found that the signals from UI-5 disappeared and reappeared several times at the receiver moorings during the 2-year experiment. We found this intriguing and started to investigate if the environmental conditions were causing the temporary disappearance of the signals. In this paper, we focus on the receptions of signals from UI-5 obtained at UI-4. We assumed that the source at UI-5 worked during the whole experiment, and we investigated if the missing receptions could be explained by: 1) change in source depth due to mooring motion; 2) the ice conditions; or 3) changes in the oceanographic fields.

The motion of each mooring was monitored throughout the experiment, showing that the source at UI-5 dived down by about 200 m, while the UI-4 receiver mooring dived down with only a couple of meters. Satellite remote sensing data showed that the ice conditions between the two moorings varied between partially and fully ice-covered during the experiment.

Oceanographic profiles from CTD/XBT data along the track were available at the beginning and end of the experiment. The oceanographic sections showed that the typical strong vertical stratification was present under the ice-covered western side of the strait. The relatively cold and fresh water near the surface was overlaying the warmer water masses below, but this layer disappeared when moving into the ice-free area. This transition zone is related to the location of the MIZ (e.g., Johannessen et al., 2003). Sea ice observations from satellites were available daily, while XBT profiles along the track were only obtained at the beginning and end of the experiment. Other oceanographic data were not obtained along the section during the experiment.

7.2.3 Ice-Ocean Re-analysis

Since few oceanographic data were available along the track, a 4D ocean state reanalysis was used to obtain information about the changes in oceanographic conditions during the experiment. The reanalysis is based on the GECCO model using the 4DVAR assimilation of sea ice from remote sensing, ocean data from moorings and buoys (Lyu et al., 2021). This reanalysis was done under the INTAROS project. Atmospheric forcing fields were from the 6-hourly National Centers for Environmental Prediction reanalysis 1 (NCEP-RA1) (Kalnay et al., 1996), including 2-m air temperature, 10-m wind vectors, precipitation rate, 2-m specific humidity, downward longwave radiation, and net shortwave radiation, as well as computed surface momentum, heat, and freshwater fluxes. The reanalysis provided ocean state estimates on a grid represented by 50 vertical z-levels ranging from 10 m at the surface to 456 m in the deep ocean. In the horizontal, a curvilinear grid with a resolution of ~ 16 km was used. Prior to the acoustic modeling, the oceanographic fields were interpolated to a curvilinear grid with a resolution of ~ 2 km.

7.2.4 Acoustic model

The Bellhop model is an acoustic numerical model based on the ray theory (Porter, 2011). The model is computationally efficient and has intuitive physical meaning for wide applications. The model has a module that can add range independent sea ice reflection coefficient to calculate sound propagation in the ice-covered regions. However, the range-dependent sea ice conditions characterizing the MIZ are not included in the Bellhop model. In this study, we used a model with a modified sea ice module to simulate acoustic propagation under range dependent sea ice ranging from open ocean to fully ice covered. Time series of the interpolated oceanographic fields were used in the Bellhop model as well as sea ice information along the track.

In the modified model, each ray is tagged with information on where it hits the sea-ice interface and at what incidence angle. The horizontal distance from the sound source, gives the ice thickness from the reanalysis. This ice thickness and incidence angle were used to search for corresponding reflection coefficient for calculation of reflection loss in the Bellhop model. Thus, the range dependent sea ice characteristics (thickness, etc.) were included. Therefore, the modified Bellhop model can be used in MIZ.

7.3 Verification of the reanalysis for use in the acoustic simulations

The sound speed section from the reanalysis data was compared with XBT/CTD sound speed data to verify the use of reanalysis as input to the acoustic model in Fig.2. Panel (a) shows the sound speed derived from the XBT/CTD data obtained between UI-5 and UI-4 during deployment in 2014. Data from 21 profiles were interpolated onto a grid with a resolution of 1 km in range and 10 m in depth. It can be clearly seen from these observations that there is a layer with a sound speed of less than 1450 m/s caused by cold and less saline water near the surface between the moorings. The thickness of the low sound speed layer varies from 10 m to 180 m (the surface duct, red line). There is another minimum in sound speed near 800 m (purple line), forming the

axis of a deep sound speed channel. The depth of this sound speed minimum rises along the section towards UI-4. Hence the area typically has a strong shallow sound speed channel and a weaker deep sound speed channel with stronger horizontal variability.

In panel (b), the section of ocean sound speed was obtained from the reanalysis data from the time of deployment, 11-12 September 2014. A total of 101 profiles were obtained with ~ 2 km horizontal separation and values at 44 depths. The profiles were interpolated to the same grid as the observations in panel (a). The shallow sound speed channel is marked by the dashed red line in panel (b). The deep sound channel is still observed but with less variability compared to observations (panel (a)). The cold-water layer coincides with the presence of sea ice and disappears near the source area where there is no ice. The deep sound channel rises from 1100 m in the western part to 300 m in the eastern part of the section. The change in sound channel depth is mostly dependent on the ocean environment and the presence of sea ice. Panel (c) shows that the sound speed from the reanalysis is generally larger than from the XBT/CTD data. The largest differences are found within the upper 50 m between 40 km and 100 km, where the model does not show the same extension of the surface duct as the observations.

Figure 2. Profiles and sections of ocean sound speed between UI-5 and UI-4 obtained on 11-12 September 2014, where the bottom is shown in brown. The red dashed line is the surface duct, and the purple dashed line is the deep sound channel. (a) is from the XBT/CTD data. (b) is from the GECCO reanalysis and (c) is the difference between (a) and (b). The profiles to the left are range-averaged sound speed for (a), (b) and (c), respectively.

The model produces realistic ice cover because it assimilates sea ice concentration from satellite data, which are quite accurate on scales larger than 10 km. Since the sea ice influences the upper ocean, we can expect that the model is also quite realistic just under the ice. However, the ice edge position can change quickly, and it can be difficult to correlate with the oceanographic conditions under the sea ice. For example, when the XBT data were collected, the ice was covering the whole section, and the surface duct was observed across the section. However, during the same time period, the ice was only covering half the section in the reanalysis. The surface duct is only observed in the western half of the track. The distribution of sound speed in the model is generally in agreement with observations, but as expected, there are differences in the upper ocean where the fronts and mesoscale activities take place. Furthermore, the front and horizontal gradients in the upper 1000 m in the reanalysis are much weaker than in the observed data. The reanalysis assimilates very few oceanographic profiles in this region, and therefore, it is the physics of the model that decides the ocean conditions under the ice, and full agreement with data is not to be expected. In addition, the resolution of the model is too coarse to pick up all the processes (e.g., eddies and fronts), correctly.

There is a reasonably good agreement between the reanalysis and observation in the deeper part of the ocean, and the model can represent realistic phenomena such as surface ducts and other gradients in the shallower layers. Based on this the reanalysis fields will be our ocean – laboratory and used to provide sea ice information and oceanographic fields as input to the acoustic model.

7.4 Acoustic propagation in the MIZ

Four days (12.09.2014, 06.09.2015, 15.01.2016, 15.05.2016) were selected to investigate sound propagation in more detail under different ice-ocean conditions. Maps of ice extent and thickness from the reanalysis are shown in Fig. 3 for the selected dates, showing that the ice conditions between UI5 and UI-4 varied significantly during the experiment. Panel (a) shows that most of the area was covered with 1-3 m thick ice, except near the UI-5 mooring. In panel (b), nearly one year after (a), the ice-cover was thinner than 1 m. In panel (c) the thickness had grown significantly in the western part from September 2015 to January 2016, whereas more of the eastern part became ice-free. In panel (d) UI-5 was embedded in sea ice and the whole section was covered by ice with thickness from 1 m to 3 m.

Subsequently, we used the Bellhop model to simulate the sound propagation for the selected days. The parameters used in the Bellhop model are given in Table 2.

Figure 3. Maps of sea ice thickness distribution from GECCO reanalysis on the four selected days. The red stars show the locations of UI-5 and UI-4. The black dots mark the positions of XBT/CTD data.

Table 2. The Bellhop model Inputs.

Parameter				Value	
Environment					
Frequency				250	Hz
Range				200	km
Environment			depth	3.5	km
Transmission			loss	coherent	
Bottom surface				acoustic half-space	
Source					
Source				600	m
Start	Angle	(from	depth	-90°	
		horizontal)			
End	Angle	(from	horizontal)	90°	
		horizontal)			
No. beams				1,800	
Receivers					

Number	horizontal	201	
Number	vertical	3501	
Main receiver	depth	200	m
Max receiver range		200	km

The segments of sea ice used in the simulations were simplified to flat elastic layers of different ice thickness with no roughness. Furthermore, the sea surface is assumed to be single layer described by the physical parameters shown in Table 1. From this, the reflection coefficients for different ice thicknesses were obtained, and a reflection coefficient file was generated. This file is used as input to the Bellhop model. Ice thickness for each segment along the section was used to select the right reflection coefficient.

Table 1. Sea ice physical parameters.

Parameter	P-wave velocity	S-wave velocity	density	Longitudinal wave absorption [11]	Shear wave absorption [11]
Value	3593.4m/s	1819.8m/s	917kg/m ³	$\alpha = 0.06f$ dB/m	$\beta = 6\alpha$ dB/m

Figure 4 shows the ocean sound speed (SSP) section between UI-5 and UI-4 extracted from the reanalysis for the same days as in Figure 3.

Figure 4. Case studies of SSP between UI-5 and UI-4 on (a) 12.09.2014, (b) 06.09.2015, (c) 15.01.2016, and (d) 15.05.2016. In each panel, the colormap shows the sound speed with the averaged ice thickness on top (the blue area marks ice thickness) and profile of range-averaged sound is shown to the right. The acoustic rays (Angle: -5-5 11) from the source at 600 m are marked by thin black lines. The purple dashed lines indicate the deep sound channels, and the red line indicates a surface duct.

It is clearly observed in all panels in Fig. 4 that the depth of the deep sound channel (in purple) is strongly related to the distribution of ice thickness, where it is deeper in open water and shallower in ice areas. It is also seen that each case has different vertical and horizontal gradients in the sound speed in the upper 1000 m with different distribution of rays. This shows that the acoustic propagation is strongly affected by the oceanographic and sea ice conditions in the MIZ.

In panel (a), the sound rays propagating upwards are reflected downwards without reaching the surface because of a 200 m thick layer of higher sound speed underneath the open water. This layer extends 100 km from UI-5 where as it weakens and finally disappears. In the same region the deep sound channel rises very quickly from ~1100 m to ~400 m over 20 km. This allows the rays to reach and interact with the ice cover until they reach UI-4. However, the rays are split into two groups, one penetrating deeper than the other. Both groups reach the surface but at different range intervals.

In Panel b) we observe layer of higher sound speed above the source, but the layer only extends about to 20 km from the source. This layer of higher sound speed prevents the rays from reaching the surface. In this region the deep sound channel rises from ~1300 m to ~ 600 m, allowing the rays to reach the surface and interact with the ice. The sound speed channel shallows gradually from ~ 600 to ~ 400 m as it approaches UI-4.

In panel (c), the deep sound channel rises gradually from UI-5 towards UI-4. Furthermore, a thin layer of lower sound speed overlays a relatively weak plume of high sound speed. The depth and the strength of the core of the plume is gradually reduced into the ice-covered region till the plume disappears at 100 km. Some deep rays seem to be undisturbed by the plume of high sound speed. However, quite a few rays are trapped above the plume till the plume rises and disappears at 100 km. From there these rays start mingling with the deeper going rays.

For panel (d), the sound source depth is situated within the plume of high sound speed. Therefore, the rays can propagate both upwards and downwards, but after once surface reflection they are bent downwards when they pass through this zone. After this all the rays continue as deep going rays, but with no distinct groups. There is a jump of the deep sound channel near 70 km in the range from ~1100 m to ~400 m, which together with gradients in the upper ocean can cause the rather messy ray pattern.

7.5 Sensitivity to mooring motion.

The sensitivity of acoustic receptions to varying source depth due to mooring motion is described in this section. In Figure 5, panel (a) shows the time series of source depth variation during the whole experiment. The source dived from 600 m down to a maximum near 800 m below the surface, while the receiver mooring only dived by a few meters (not shown). The varying source depths were used as input to the Bellhop model, together with the corresponding oceanographic fields. Panel (b) shows the time series of arriving rays at different receiver depths and the source depth from (a). Panel (c) shows the number of arrivals using a fixed source depth at 600m. The difference between b) and c) is shown in panel (d). It is observed that the variation of source depth between 600-800 has little effect on the number of acoustic arrivals. From this, we conclude that changes in acoustic receptions caused by environmental parameters are much stronger than the impact of varying source depth due to mooring motion. In particular, it is observed that the periods with very few receptions are present both when the source depth is varying and when the source is fixed. Therefore, in the following analysis, we use a fixed source depth at 600 m in the acoustic model.

Figure 5 (a) source depth as a function of time, (b) the number of arrivals at UI-4 using the varying source depths. (c) the number of arrivals at UI-4 using a fixed source depth of 600m, (d) the difference of the number of arrivals between (b) and (c).

7.6 Sensitivity to environmental parameters

The time series of the range average sound speed profile between UI-5 and UI-4 is shown in Fig. 6a. The range averages are calculated daily from 01.09.2014 to 31.07.2016 based on the reanalysis. The strength and the

thickness of the upper layer of low sound varies with time. The higher sound speed in the deeper water masses is varies with time. The depth of the minimum sound speed in the upper 200 m is shown in Fig. 6b, while the sea ice extension and thickness is shown in Fig 6c. There is no clear seasonal variability in any of the timeseries. However, the periods with larger extension of the deep sound speed channel (red in b) and the periods with high sound speed in a) seem to correspond. Comparing b) with c) shows that the depth of the deep sound channel partly varies with the ice cover, but that the sea ice variability is more rapid and stronger than the changes in the water masses. The deeper ocean does not adjust quickly to changes in the ice conditions, which is expected.

The daily range dependent sound speed profiles and ice distributions along the track are used as input to the Bellhop model. For each day, the number of arrivals at different receiving depths are calculated for a source depth of 600 m. In the number of arrivals, only the rays with energy above a mean level were calculated using the energy from all the arrived rays. The result of the calculations is shown in Figure 6 d.

The lowest number of receptions occurs in the upper 200 m when the sound rays are trapped in the deep sound channel. The reception is better when the environment allows the sound rays to be trapped in the cold-water layer. The most stable and good receptions are found for receivers between 200~1000m.

Figure 6. Time series of (a) sound speed profile (SSP), (b) depth of minimum sound, (c) sea ice thickness, and (d) the number of arrivals at the receiver depth, all based on input field from the reanalysis. The former three variables are used in the Bellhop model to calculate the arrivals. The black arrows correspond to the dates 12.09.2014, 06.09.2015, 15.01.2016, respectively, which are the same as in Fig. 3 and 4.

In figure 6 b it is observed how rapidly the depth of the deep sound speed minimum is reduced from around 1400 meters to 400 meters. This indicates the location and strength of the oceanographic (temperature) gradients. It is observed in figure 6 d that the lowest number of arrivals are during periods when the strong gradients happen at short ranges. If, however, this gradient is located at further away from the source e.g. between 50-150 km there are generally more arrivals. For example, the number of arrivals is high during September to November 2014 and from December 2015 to July 2016 this is when the oceanographic gradient is located at ranges of the order of 100 km. While, during August and September in 2015 the oceanographic gradient is only around 25 km away from the source, and the number of arrivals are very low during this period. Based on this we claim that the poor receiving conditions are related to periods when strong oceanographic gradients are located relatively close to the source mooring.

7.7 Configuration of instruments

In this section, we investigate how the receptions can be improved by changing the configuration of the receivers or the source on the moorings. In Fig. 7, the numbers of received rays are calculated and presented as a function of receiver depths and source depths on the four selected days (same days as in Fig 3 and 4). As in Fig. 6, only rays with energy above a mean level are included. The red (blue) colors indicate higher (lower) efficiency of acoustic energy transmission. The red box illustrates the receiver depths and the variable source depths during the UNDER-ICE experiment.

Figure 7. The number of received rays as a function of receiver depths and source depths on (a) 12.09.2014, (b) 06.09.2015, (c) 15.01.2016, and (d) 15.05.2016. The colors indicate the efficiency of the acoustic energy transmission.

The number of arrivals at all receiver depths in (a), (c), and (d) are higher than in (b) for all the source depths. From this, we conclude that the lowest transmission conditions occur when the shallowing of the deep sound channel is close to the source (Fig 6). Furthermore, we can observe that the number of received rays are more sensitive to the source depth than the receiver depth.

In (a) the strongest signals are found for the deepest receivers (800 m - 1200 m) for source depths shallower than 400 m. For deeper source depths, most of the sound rays are received at shallower receivers between 200 m and 600 m. The situation is the opposite in (c). For shallow source depths, less than 200 m, most of the sound rays are received above 500 m near the surface. For source depths from 200 m and 700 m, most of the rays are received between 500 m and 1200 m. For the source deeper than 700 m, a significant number of sound rays can be received almost at any depth.

In (d) the sound rays are received at all receiver depths considered for source depths shallower than 700 m. For deeper source depths, fewer rays are received at depths shallower than 200 m.

The receiver configuration and the variable source depths used in the experiment are shown by the red rectangle. The number of received rays within this rectangle is rather low and indicates that the configuration was not optimal for the four selected days. In particular, for case b) the number of received rays was low for all source depths and all receiver depths when strong oceanographic gradients were close to the source.

Comparing the four panels in Figure 7, we observe that a change in the configuration of the source and receivers to improve the number of arrivals in most of the cases. The suggested configuration is indicated by the black rectangle, which show a high number of received rays from 200m down to 1200 m for source depths around 500 m for all panels except (b). When the oceanographic front is close to the source, as in (b), there is no optimal solution. In all the other cases, a doubling the length of the receiver array would further improve the experiment significantly.

7.8 Discussion and conclusion

The Bellhop model with a modified sea ice module has been used to simulate range-dependent acoustic propagation in the MIZ using time series of ice-ocean data from a reanalysis based on GECCO. The main goal of the study was to find out if this particular environment or mooring motion could cause the acoustic

receptions to disappear for long periods during the UNDER-ICE experiment. Furthermore, it was a goal to investigate if a better source and receiver configuration could have improved the results of the experiment.

From our study, we can conclude that variable sound source depth due to mooring motion had a minor effect on the reception of the acoustic signal compared to the effect of changing ocean environment.

Furthermore, our study confirms that the oceanographic conditions can make it hard to transmit signal from a source outside the ice edge to a receiver array inside the ice edge for any source/receiver configuration. The worst conditions are if there are strong horizontal gradients in the oceanographic conditions close to the source. The simulation results show that the configuration of source and receiver array can be optimized to accommodate better receptions in most of the oceanographic conditions considered in our study. Therefore, we suggest modifying the configuration by lowering the receiver array and putting the source at a shallower depth (500 m) in future acoustic experiments in the Fram Strait marginal ice zone.

Our findings have consequences for low frequency communication and underwater geo-positioning (UW-GPS). The sound source used in the UNDER-ICE experiment produced a broadband sweep from 200-300 Hz. A narrow band (1.5 Hz bandwidth) at 250 Hz RAOS signal are used by gliders to navigate and postprocessing for geo-positioning of underwater floats. Therefore, our analysis will be useful for understanding the capability and limitations of gliders and floats to receive signals in a network of acoustic sources in the Marginal Ice Zone e.g. which listening depths will be the optimal and under what conditions will the signal be difficult to receive. The study also provides insight into communication capabilities in the Marginal Ice Zone at frequencies between 200-300 Hz.

In our model study, we used smooth sea ice with variable thickness. The effect of scattering from a rough underside of the ice will make the transmission of signals even more complex. The next step in our study is to study how to include a scattering from the sea ice in our acoustic simulations along with other frequencies.

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